

Towards sustainable wellbeing: Integrated policies and transformative indicators.

Pathways to Sustainable Wellbeing in Ecuador

WP3 – ToBe Ecuador Team Report | 2024 Fieldwork Findings

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Document History

Deliverable Title	Pathways to sustainable Wellbeing in Ecuador
Brief Description	This report presents preliminary findings from the 2024 fieldwork carried out by the ToBe Ecuador team as part of Work Package 3. Through qualitative research, it explores the dynamics of sustainable wellbeing in Indigenous and rural communities from two key regions: Imbabura (Andean highlands) and Napo (Amazonian lowlands). The study includes four case studies: UNORCAC, UNCISA, and Sumak Yaku in Imbabura, and the Kallari Association in Napo. The report analyzes local understandings of wellbeing, technology, and sustainability, as well as structural drivers and barriers to community-based initiatives. These preliminary insights contribute to the co-creation of context-sensitive transformative indicators and integrated policy strategies aligned with diverse worldviews and territorial realities.
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Executive Summary

This report presents the main findings of the 2024 fieldwork conducted by the ToBe Ecuador team, focusing on sustainable wellbeing in Indigenous and rural communities in the provinces of Imbabura and Napo. Through qualitative research methods, including interviews, workshops, and participant observation, the study analyzed the experiences of organizations such as UNORCAC, UNCISA, Sumak Yaku, and the Kallari Association. The research was guided by post-development and Buen Vivir frameworks, examining local understandings of wellbeing, technology, and sustainability, as well as the barriers and drivers shaping community initiatives.

The results reveal a significant gap between national public policies and the realities of Indigenous territories, emphasizing the importance of recognizing diverse worldviews and lived experiences. By highlighting community-led approaches to sustainability and reciprocity, the findings contribute to the ToBe Project’s broader goal of developing transformative indicators and integrated policies that support transitions toward sustainable wellbeing both in Ecuador and internationally.

About ToBe

ToBe is a 3-year project funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe framework programme. Tampere University (Finland) acts as a coordinator for the project.

The ToBe project aims at studying the way in which mindsets, indicators, innovations, and policies could better work together towards a sustainability paradigm. The need for moving toward a sustainability paradigm has been widely called for, yet the path to achieving that is not clear. ToBe aims to contribute to filling this gap and create an understanding of a sustainable wellbeing economy through integrated policies and transformative indicators.

The ToBe consortium brings together acknowledged scholars with previous high-quality research on the topic and with diverse backgrounds from social sciences, ecological and political economy, environmental and innovation studies, science and technology, data science, AI and machine learning. All partners represent well-known and established universities, other research institutions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Table 1 lists the members of the consortium, which consists of 13 beneficiaries and one associated partner.

Table 1. ToBe Consortium Members

No	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country
1	COO	TAU	TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	FI
2	BEN	SU	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SE

3	BEN	VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY	FI
4	BEN	EURADA	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE DES AGENCESDE DEVELOPPEMENT	BE
5	BEN	Sciences Po	FONDATION NATIONALE DES SCIENCES POLITIQUES	FR
6	BEN	ICHEC	HAUTE ECOLE ICHEC - ECAM - ISFSC	BE
7	BEN	IPE	INSTITUT ZA POLITICKU EKOLOGIJU	HR
8	BEN	UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
9	BEN	Ugent	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	BE
10	BEN	EPC	EUROPEAN POLICY CENTRE	BE
11	BEN	UAB	UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA	ES
12	BEN	EPN Ecuador	ESCUELA POLITECNICA NACIONAL	EC
13	BEN	CHAL	CHALMERS TEKNISKA HOGSKOLA AB	SE
14	Associated partner	UnivLeeds	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UK

The main objective of ToBe is to contribute to a clearer understanding of how to move to a sustainability paradigm. More specifically, ToBe aims at achieving the following objectives:

- Construct a theoretical framework for a sustainable wellbeing economy by providing a systemic and dynamic understanding of how changing policy goals, mindsets, indicators, innovations and policies work together towards a sustainability paradigm.
- Identify different processes of economic growth by analysing their social and environmental implications.
- Evaluate and compare alternative growth initiatives as systemic innovations with a focus on drivers and barriers to implementation and impacts.
- Develop an ecological macroeconomic model combining conventional macroeconomic variables with indicators of wellbeing and sustainability to assess policies from a multidimensional perspective, and to reveal the synergies and trade-offs inherent in the transition to sustainability.
- Co-create policy solutions together with stakeholders to help institutionalise the new policies and indicators in Europe and beyond (potentially including South American and African countries).

1. Introduction

This report presents the work carried out by the ToBe Ecuador team under Work Package 3, corresponding to qualitative research activities conducted throughout 2024 in the Andean and Amazonian regions of the country. The document systematizes the main findings from fieldwork with Indigenous communities and grassroots organizations, focusing on the interconnections between sustainable wellbeing, public policies, regulatory frameworks, and transformative indicators from a situated perspective.

The report is structured into seven main sections. It begins by contextualizing the Ecuadorian case, emphasizing its territorial, socioeconomic, and cultural diversity, as well as structural tensions related to prevailing development models. This is followed by the theoretical and conceptual framework guiding the analysis, with a focus on post-development approaches and Buen Vivir (Sumak Kawsay), which are particularly relevant for understanding alternative conceptions of wellbeing in the territories studied.

Next, the report provides a critical review of national public policies and legal instruments linked to sustainable wellbeing, including the 2008 Constitution, development plans, specific laws, and sectoral strategies. This section allows for an assessment of the coherence and gaps between institutional frameworks and local realities.

The methodological chapter outlines the research design and case selection criteria, along with the methods used: semi-structured interviews, participant observation, workshops, and community feedback mechanisms. Four case studies are examined: UNORCAC and UNCISA in Imbabura; Sumak Yaku and the Kallari Association in Napo.

Findings are organized into three main analytical blocks: structural barriers and enabling conditions for sustainability in Indigenous contexts; local understandings of wellbeing, sustainability, and technology; and experiences of reciprocity and knowledge co-production throughout the research process. The final section offers reflections on the implications of these findings for the overall goals of the ToBe project, particularly regarding the development of context-sensitive transformative indicators, and highlights key learnings for designing integrated policies toward sustainable wellbeing.

1.2. Ecuadorian Context

The Republic of Ecuador is located in South America and covers 270,670 km² (Secretaría Nacional de Planificación y Desarrollo, 2017). Of the land dedicated to production at the national level, 5.20 million hectares are used for agriculture (permanent and seasonal crops and cultivated and natural pastures) (INEC, 2020). The country is divided into four regions: highland, coast, insular (Galapagos Islands) and Amazon (Figure 1a–c), with extraordinarily diverse ecosystems suitable for research and the development of a great variety of agricultural activities.

Figure 1. (a) Characteristics of Ecuador's population. (b) Production Structure and Agricultural Performance in Ecuador. (c) Evolution of Agro-industrial and Agricultural Gross Value Added (GVA) in Ecuador: Absolute Figures and GDP Share (2010-2020)

Currently, Ecuador has 17,023,408 inhabitants. According to the three-sector model of economic activities, the primary sector involves the extraction of raw materials, in which 19% of Ecuador’s economically active population (EAP) is employed; the secondary sector is dedicated to manufacturing and employs 13% of the EAP; and the tertiary sector, employing 66% of the EAP, is made up of service industries that facilitate the transport, distribution and sale of goods produced by the secondary sector. The primary sector, which includes agriculture, livestock production, forestry and fishing, is among the principal activities in most provinces, has a stimulating effect on Ecuador’s overall economy (Figure 1a–c) and accounts for 12% of the gross value added (GVA). The GVA is the difference between production and intermediate consumption and contributes directly to the country’s gross domestic product (GDP) (Banco Central del Ecuador, 2017).

Ecuador’s biodiversity is among its greatest riches (Cuesta et al., 2020). Unfortunately, it is affected by deforestation (Kleemann et al., 2022) due to the expansion of the agricultural frontier [13], other extractive processes (Mestanza-Ramón et al., 2022), urbanization processes and other human interventions (Iñiguez-Armijos et al., 2022). Another issue that has yet to be adequately addressed is soil and water pollution (Chancay et al., 2021) resulting from intensive agricultural practices that include the increased use of chemicals and fertilisers (Heredia et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Characteristics of Imbabura province’s population and agricultural production.

The province of Imbabura has a total area of 4,588 km² and a population of 469,879 inhabitants, according to data from the *Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos* (2022). The population is almost evenly distributed between urban and rural zones, with a slight predominance in urban

areas (245,628 people). Women make up the majority of the population, representing 51.8%. In terms of ethnic self-identification, the population is predominantly mixed-race (mestizo), accounting for 64.9% of the total. The Indigenous population represents a significant portion at 28%, followed by Afro-Ecuadorians (5.8%), white (1.0%), and Montubio (0.3%) (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022).

Regarding agricultural production, soft corn is the dominant crop in Imbabura, with a total of 20,584 hectares cultivated. Other important crops include beans (2,731 ha), artisanal sugarcane (1,606 ha), and barley (1,370 ha). The province also cultivates fruit trees, tamarillo, potato, dent corn, and avocado, reflecting a high level of crop diversity (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019) These indicators highlight the socio-demographic diversity and the agricultural potential of Imbabura, which remains a key province in Ecuador’s food system.

Figure 3. Characteristics of Cotacachi’s population and agricultural production

Cotacachi has a total population of 53,001 inhabitants, with the majority living in rural areas (42,475 people). According to the most recent census (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022), women slightly outnumber men, representing 50.7% of the population. In terms of ethnic identification, 53.6% of Cotacacheños identify as mestizo, while 41.7% identify as

Indigenous. This highlights a strong presence of Indigenous communities in the territory (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022).

Basic services coverage remains a challenge. Only 49.9% of the population has access to a sewage system, although 77.3% have piped water supply. Agriculturally, soft corn is the leading crop, with 3,420 hectares cultivated. Other important crops include beans (906 ha), dent corn (612 ha), and plantain (585 ha). Cotacachi also maintains crop diversity with heart of palm, barley, tamarillo, and artisanal sugarcane (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019). These figures reflect Cotacachi’s strong rural identity, its cultural diversity, and its vital role in Ecuador’s agricultural landscape.

Figure 4. Characteristics of Napo province’s population and agricultural production

Napo is a predominantly rural province located in the Amazon region of Ecuador, with a total area of 12,543 km² and a population of 131,675 inhabitants (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022). Most people—87,000—live in rural areas, while the remaining 44,675 reside in urban zones. Gender distribution is balanced, with 50.2% women and 49.8% men. Ethnic identification data reveals that 65% of the population identify as Indigenous, followed by 32.5% as mestizo and 1.3% as Afro-Ecuadorian. This highlights the strong Indigenous presence and cultural richness of the region (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022).

In terms of agricultural production, cacao is the most important crop in Napo, with 4,350 hectares cultivated. Other relevant crops include plantain (1,129 ha), dent corn (1,050 ha), coffee (890 ha), and cacao-chocolate varieties (780 ha). The province also grows cassava, fruit trees, sugarcane, and other miscellaneous crops, showcasing considerable biodiversity (MAG, 2019). Regarding the distribution of agricultural land, the canton of Tena holds the largest share, with 91.38% of Napo's agricultural surface (7,671 hectares). Other cantons like Carlos

Julio Arosemena Tola, Archidona, El Chaco, and Quijos contribute minimally, with fewer than 400 hectares each (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019).

Figure 5. Characteristics of Tena’s population and agricultural production

Tena, the capital of Napo province, has a population of 80,816 inhabitants, with most residents (42,475) living in rural areas. According to census data (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022), Indigenous people are the majority, comprising 67.0% of the local population, while 30.5% identify as mestizo. In terms of gender, the population is balanced, with 50.3% women and 49.7% men. Despite relatively high access to piped water supply (76.2%), only 47.4% of the population has access to sewage services, indicating significant gaps in sanitation infrastructure.

Agriculturally, cacao is the dominant crop, with 4,019 hectares cultivated in 2022. Other key crops include plantain (1,093 ha), dent corn (1,041 ha), and coffee (558 ha). Tena also cultivates a variety of small-scale crops such as cacao-coffee hybrids, cassava, fruit trees, and passion fruit, showcasing the canton’s agricultural diversity (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019).

The cantons of Tena (in Napo Province) and Cotacachi (in Imbabura Province) represent two distinct territorial realities in Ecuador in terms of demographics, ethnic composition, basic services, and agricultural production.

Population and Settlement Patterns: Tena has a larger population, with 80,816 inhabitants, compared to Cotacachi's 53,001 (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022). In both cantons, the population is predominantly rural: 42,475 in Tena and the same number in Cotacachi. Urban populations are relatively small—10,526 in Tena and 10,526 in Cotacachi—highlighting their rural character.

Gender Distribution: In both cantons, women slightly outnumber men, making up 50.3% of the population in Tena and 50.7% in Cotacachi. This reflects a balanced gender distribution.

Ethnic Identification: Tena has a significantly higher percentage of Indigenous population (67.0%), whereas in Cotacachi, the majority is mestizo (53.6%), with 41.7% Indigenous (Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos, 2022). This contrast illustrates differing cultural and demographic identities: Tena as a predominantly Indigenous territory, and Cotacachi as a more ethnically mixed area.

Access to Basic Services: Cotacachi shows slightly better infrastructure in terms of sewage access, with 49.9% coverage compared to 47.4% in Tena. However, Tena has a higher piped water supply coverage, at 76.2%, compared to 77.3% in Cotacachi—both relatively high but still reflecting rural challenges in sanitation systems.

Agricultural Production: Agriculture is vital in both cantons, but the main crops differ

- In Tena, the leading crop is cacao, with 4,019 hectares cultivated. Other significant crops include plantain, dent corn, and coffee. The crop diversity includes cassava, fruit trees, and passion fruit (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019).
- In Cotacachi, the main crop is soft corn, with 3,420 hectares. It also grows beans, dent corn, plantain, and artisanal sugarcane, with additional diversity in crops like tamarillo and barley (Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería del Ecuador, 2019).

This shows that while both territories have diversified agriculture, Tena's economy is more strongly linked to cacao and tropical crops, reflecting its Amazonian climate, while Cotacachi's agriculture is more Andean, focusing on grains and temperate crops. Tena and Cotacachi present two contrasting rural models in Ecuador. Tena stands out for its strong Indigenous presence and tropical agricultural economy centered on cacao, while Cotacachi reflects a more mixed demographic profile and Andean-style agriculture focused on corn and beans. These differences highlight the territorial, cultural, and agro-ecological diversity that shapes rural development strategies in Ecuador.

2. Theoretical-Conceptual Framework

2.1. Post-Development

The post-development current emerges as a critical response to the conventional development paradigm. It is not conceived as a specific stage to be achieved, but rather as a broad category and decolonial approach that questions the Eurocentric foundations of modern development. From this perspective, development (understood in its Western and linear form) ceases to be the organizing axis of social life, making way for plural and localized visions originating from Indigenous peoples, local communities, women’s movements, and other civil society groups—that is, those who have traditionally been seen as “victims” of development.

Post-development emphasizes the need for epistemological pluralism, placing local knowledge at the center and exploring alternative ways of meeting human needs within planetary boundaries. In short, it proposes to “decenter” dominant development in order to open discursive space for other paths to wellbeing and social organization.

2.1.1. Critiques of the Conventional Development Paradigm

Post-development authors present a deep critique of the assumptions and consequences of conventional development. Arturo Escobar distinguishes two levels of critique: first, the proposals of “alternative developments” (e.g., human development, sustainable development), which continued operating within the same framework and offered only partial solutions; and second, the post-development critique, which understands that the issue is not just the limitations of development but the hegemony of development as discourse.

This second critique does not seek a reformed version of “another development,” but rather questions how the very idea emerged that certain societies were “underdeveloped” according to Western parameters. According to Ziai (2017), most post-development authors share several core arguments in their critiques, including:

1. **Development as a discursive invention:** The creation of the notion of “developed” vs. “underdeveloped” countries (e.g., Truman’s 1949 speech).
2. **Ambiguity of the concept:** “Development” is a vague and malleable term—an amoeba concept lacking precise definition.
3. **Non-neutral knowledge:** Representations of the world under the idea of development imply power relations; the knowledge underpinning conventional development is neither objective nor universal.

4. **Hegemonic Eurocentrism:** The Western worldview is imposed as a universal standard of progress, placing local cultures beneath that benchmark.
5. **Negative consequences:** Development has generated impoverishment, inequality, and exclusion, especially in the global peripheries.
6. **Unlimited growth economy:** There is a critique of the obsession with economic categories focused on growth, productivity, and the satisfaction of infinite needs—normalizing an unsustainable model.
7. **Resistance and alternatives:** There is an emphasis on movements that resist imposed development and are committed to generating post-development alternatives.

From the post-development perspective, even mainstream narratives such as sustainable development or the green economy are viewed with skepticism, as they often represent “false solutions” that preserve the economist paradigm. These technocratic proposals are criticized for aiming to mitigate environmental problems without questioning the imperative of economic growth—leading to paradoxes such as trying to reduce ecological risks while promoting ever-increasing consumption.

Likewise, concepts such as “natural capital” tend to commodify nature, masking continued exploitation with economic language. In essence, post-development denounces that neo-developmental solutions perpetuate the hegemony of Western development instead of truly breaking away from it.

2.1.2. Alternative Perspectives

In the face of these criticisms, post-development explores and legitimizes the emergence of new perspectives and initiatives aimed at overcoming economic growth as the only horizon. These alternatives are inscribed in a pluriversal imaginary framework, that is, the idea that there is not a single path of “development” but multiple worlds and forms of well-being coexisting. Contemporary authors stress that it is not a rejection of everything Western or science, but of defending the diversity of visions and ways of life that emerge from empirical experiences around the world. As Escobar (2005) points out, following Zapatista thought, there is a struggle for “a world where many worlds fit,” valuing indigenous worldviews, traditional knowledge, and community ways of life that had been marginalized. Instead of naively idealizing the “autochthonous,” it advocates that *all societies*—not just indigenous ones—try to live “between worlds,” accepting interdependence and (re)communalizing everyday existence beyond capitalist individualism.

In practice, post-developmental thought is related to several emerging imaginaries that share the search for civilizational alternatives. For example, there is an affinity with post-

capitalism proposals, which question the capacity of capitalism to organize the entire economy; with de-growth or post-growth, which proposes to decenter growth from the center of economic and social life; with feminist and post-patriarchal currents that challenge the dominant logics of male power; with anti-racist movements that combat colonial inequalities; and with decoloniality that seeks to detach the production of knowledge from its Eurocentric bias. In the same way, alternative concepts and practices have been articulated, such as Good Living, *eco-swaraj* (ecological autonomy in India), *ubuntu* (African community philosophy), solidarity economy, environmental and climate justice, food and energy sovereignty, among many others. All these initiatives, new or re-emerged, represent attempts at "alternatives to development", that is, visions of well-being and the relationship between society and nature that do not imitate the dominant developmentalist model.

A common feature in these proposals is their strong anchorage in grassroots movements and traditional knowledge. Various authors have observed that the seeds of post-development sprout in local, rural and urban communities, and in the informal sector, especially among those marginalized groups that have borne the greatest costs of unsustainable development. New social structures emerge there based on reciprocity, solidarity and the relocation of the economy, in contrast to the logic of the global market. North-South dialogues are also important: the exchange between ancestral visions of the global South and ecological quests of the North allows us to think about a global civilizational transition towards sustainable ways of life. This implies de-colonizing knowledge and breaking the sharp divisions between human beings and nature typical of the Western paradigm, moving towards a more relational and harmonious understanding of the world. In short, post-development promotes an alternative in which the good life is not measured by economic growth, but by the quality of relationships – between people, communities and with Mother Earth – laying the foundations for truly inclusive and sustainable transformation agendas.

2.2. Buen Vivir

After the Constitution of Ecuador in 2008, which includes the terms *Sumak Kawsay* (SK) and *Buen vivir* (BV), the academic field has leaned with greater potential to understand and explain the origins, their approaches and conceptualizations. As a first contextualization of interest or curiosity, search results are shown in Scopus for "good living" in a period from 2009 to 2023.

Figure 6. Documents by year on *Buen Vivir*

Fuente: Scopus- "Buen Vivir" Results- [Accessed September 2024]

Figure 7. Documents by country on *Buen Vivir*

Fuente: Scopus- "Buen Vivir" Results- [Accessed September 2024]

It is important to note that the literature review is carried out only on *Buen Vivir* as such, since, although it is directly related to *Sumak Kawsay*, they are not synonymous or exact translation from Kichwa to Spanish (harmony in life/life in fullness) (Chassagne, 2019; Cuestas-Caza, 2019). In this sense, Vásquez Bustamante et al. (2021) agree with the differentiation of *Sumak Kawsay* as part of or as a type of Good Living.

In general terms, the idea of "development" has historically been associated with economic growth, industrialization and modernization; however, the Western development model itself, promoted since the post-war period and reinforced by globalization, has generated processes of social inequality and environmental deterioration (Altmann, 2017; Zuboff, 2019). The growing commodification of nature, associated with consumerism, intensifies the exploitation of natural resources and the accumulation of waste (Tórtora, 2021; Yáñez, 2021). This panorama has provoked a series of critical reflections and anti-neoliberal social struggles in Latin America, from which Buen Vivir emerges as an alternative proposal to the hegemonic paradigm (Lucero, 2023).

Globalization, understood not only as an economic phenomenon but as a historical process, has deepened the imposition of capitalist logics and extractivism, as well as cultural homogenization (Friggeri, 2021; Maldonado, 2019). However, it has also provided spaces for the exchange of knowledge that have made it possible to disseminate Buen Vivir at an international level, encouraging the attention of European researchers and researchers from other latitudes (Pérez-Rincón et al., 2019).

The Suma Qamaña is incorporated into the Bolivian Constitution, promoting the protection of nature and a model of coexistence that emphasizes the right of indigenous peoples to live with dignity and in environmental balance (Cappelli et al., 2022). In Ecuador, the Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador (2008) recognizes nature as a subject of rights, underlines social co-responsibility in the protection of ecosystems, and advocates a development approach that prioritizes life in harmony with the environment (Calvo et al., 2020; Vela-Almeida & Torres, 2021). These regulations aspire to a plurinational, fair and sustainable society, in which the economy is not reduced to mere growth, but guarantees the fundamental rights of people and those of nature itself (Chamorro et al., 2021).

In BV, harmony with oneself, with the community, and with nature is prioritized, going beyond anthropocentrism and embracing a biocentric vision (Cubillo-Guevara & Hidalgo-Capitán, 2019). From this perspective, equality extends beyond the merely human to integrate cultural plurality, intergenerationality, and the recognition of future generations, as well as respect for the environment (Herrera et al., 2019). Indigenous experiences in countries such as Ecuador (Sarayaku and Cayambe) reflect a worldview where nature is not an exploitable resource, but a living entity with which one seeks to coexist and sustain reciprocal relationships (Lang, 2022; Ramírez-Cendrero et al., 2017).

This approach is based on principles such as relationality, reciprocity and correspondence (Mattioli, 2019). Relationality assumes that every living being is interconnected, while reciprocity implies a continuous give and take in community and environmental coexistence. Correspondence, on the other hand, conceives that what happens in a larger area is reflected in the smaller and vice versa. These principles require, in practice, an austere existence, supportive and respectful of the environment and future generations. Following Cubillo-Guevara & Hidalgo-Capitán (2019), three currents are identified around BV:

1. **Indigenist Current:** Defends the centrality of the traditions and worldviews of the native peoples, understanding Sumak Kawsay as a philosophy of community, pre-modern, and ecological life (Aguar & Blanco, 2021).
2. **Socialist Current:** It advocates for an "Andean community socialism" that privileges state management, the redistribution of wealth and social equity, without neglecting harmony with nature (Bracarense & Gil-Vasquez, 2018).
3. **Post-developmental current:** It proposes to go "beyond development" and build a plural vision that integrates indigenous, ecological, feminist and anti-capitalist perspectives, prioritizing the active participation of citizens in the definition of the very concept of BV (Aroca, 2020; Torres-Solis et al., 2019).

Despite their discrepancies, these currents coincide in the urgency of recognising the rights of nature and in the critique of the hegemonic vision of economic growth that neglects equity, interculturality and sustainability (Guerra & Álava, 2023; Laastad, 2020).

Buen Vivir emerges as a Latin American alternative to the traditional development paradigm, emphasizing harmony with nature, social inclusion and human dignity. Its incorporation into the constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia marked a milestone in recognizing the rights of nature and proposing a plurinational state where indigenous visions and public policies aimed at equity and sustainability converge (Berros, 2021; Mero-Figueroa et al., 2020). Although debates persist about the scope and practical application of BV, there is growing academic interest in valuing its relational, intercultural, and post-extractivist character, as well as its potential to inspire profound reforms in social, economic, and political organization (Cubillo-Guevara & Hidalgo-Capitán, 2019). In short, Buen Vivir represents a call to rethink the notion of "progress" and to forge more just and sustainable models, in convergence with ancestral wisdom and contemporary demands for environmental preservation and social equity.

3. Overview of Public Policy related on Sustainable Wellbeing in Ecuador

Latin America is a region marked by rich biodiversity, important natural resources, and deep cultural diversity, which makes it a key scenario for the implementation of sustainable wellbeing policies. However, the region also faces significant challenges, such as poverty, social and economic inequality, and increasing vulnerability to the effects of climate change. In this context, some Latin American governments seek to adopt policies that balance economic development with the protection of the environment and the improvement of the quality of life of their populations. ECLAC (2016) stresses that a comprehensive approach that links social equity with environmental sustainability is crucial to achieving truly inclusive and lasting development.

Latin America is home to some of the world's most biodiverse ecosystems, such as the Amazon, the Andes, and the Pantanal, which are essential not only for the region, but for global climate stability. The conservation of these resources has been a priority in the public policies of several countries, which have implemented protected areas, nature reserves, and reforestation policies to preserve their biodiversity and the ecosystem services they provide (Soares-Filho et al., 2010).

The conservation of natural resources is also closely linked to the rights and participation of local and indigenous communities, who often depend directly on these resources for their livelihoods. In this sense, public policies in countries such as Ecuador have sought to integrate traditional knowledge and practices into conservation strategies, which not only improves the effectiveness of these policies, but also empowers local communities and respects their right to participate in the management of their territories (Barkin & Fuente, 2013).

Table 2. Systematization of public policy analysis related to sustainable wellbeing in Latin America

Country	Public Policy Approach	Main challenges	Highlights
Brazil	Conservation of the Amazon and poverty reduction through the Green Bag Program (Imazon, 2017)	Increasing deforestation and economic pressure for agricultural and mining expansion	Significant initiatives for the protection of protected areas, but with mixed results due to external pressure

Mexico	Climate Change Mitigation and Sustainable Agriculture through the National Climate Change Strategy	Limitations in financing and infrastructure, uneven implementation	Progress in the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices and the transition to renewable energy (FAO, 2015)
Chile	Development of renewable energies and waste management through the Energy Policy 2050 and REP Law (Ministry of Energy of Chile, 2015)	Prolonged droughts and the need for more robust climate adaptation policies	Positioning as a leader in renewable energies in Latin America
Colombia	Protection of biodiversity and adaptation to climate change through the National Biodiversity Policy and PNACC	Conflict between conservation and economic development, especially in areas of armed conflict	Development of climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation plans (IDEAM, 2017)
Argentina	Promotion of renewable energies and sustainable agriculture through the RenovAr Program	Economic instability that affects the effective implementation of sustainable policies	Attracting investments in renewable energy, but with limited progress in sustainability due to economic crises

Own Elaboration

To carry out an analysis from the Ecuadorian public policy that contributes to sustainable wellbeing, it is first necessary to understand the different laws in force, such as the constitution as the most important legal framework in Ecuador to the public policies presented in recent years. In this sense, within the framework of sustainable well-being, we evidenced first-hand its main values. Three key needs have been defined for this understanding of sustainable well-being: Health, Need for autonomy and connection with the environment.

- **Health** is a necessity and an important precondition for physical functioning. As mammals, we need to avoid disease and survive with a preferably long lifespan. Health refers to both physical and psychological health.
- **Bonding with the environment** is a necessary part of human nature. For healthy development, individuals need love and relationship through participation in communities and everyday situations. Interdependence does not only refer to others seres humanos, sino también a otras especies. Se refiere a nuestra profunda necesidad de coexistir con todas las criaturas que comparten nuestra biosfera común.

- **The need for autonomy** refers to the self-affirmation of one's own behavior and the experience of feeling integrated. Autonomy is the ability to integrate values to guide behavior, make informed decisions, and ultimately be able to change cultural norms. The opposite of autonomy is the experience of feeling pressured to think, feel, or behave in a certain way.

Based on these principles, an analysis of public policies that conform to these principles is carried out.

3.1. Constitution of Ecuador

The Constitution of Ecuador recognizes in its second chapter the rights of Buen Vivir. In which different sections are detailed, such as Water and food, Healthy environment, Communication and information, Culture and Science, Education, Habitat and housing, Health, Labor and social security. Different articles are defined on this:

- **Art. 14.-** The right of the population to live in a healthy and ecologically balanced environment, which guarantees sustainability and good living, *sumak kawsay*, is recognized. The preservation of the environment, the conservation of ecosystems, biodiversity and the integrity of the country's genetic heritage, the prevention of environmental damage and the recovery of degraded natural spaces are declared to be of public interest.
- **Article 15.-** The State shall promote, in the public sector, the use of environmentally clean technologies and non-polluting and low-impact alternative energies. Energy sovereignty will not be achieved to the detriment of food sovereignty, nor will it affect water.
- **Article 32.-** Health is a right guaranteed by the State, the realization of which is linked to the exercise of other rights, including the right to water, food, education, physical culture, work, social security, healthy environments and others that sustain good living. The State shall guarantee this right through economic, social, cultural, educational and environmental policies; and permanent, timely and non-exclusive access to programs, actions and services for the promotion and comprehensive care of health, sexual health and reproductive health. The provision of health services will be governed by the principles of equity, universality, solidarity, interculturality, quality, efficiency, effectiveness, precaution and bioethics, with a gender and generational approach.

Chapter seven of Section III mentions the rights to nature and describes it in Article 71 as follows:

- **Article 71.-** Nature or *Pacha Mama*, where life is reproduced and realized, has the right to have its existence and the maintenance and regeneration of its vital cycles, structure,

functions and evolutionary processes fully respected. Any person, community, people or nationality may demand from the public authority the fulfilment of the rights of nature. In applying and interpreting these rights, the principles established in the Constitution shall be observed, as appropriate. The State shall encourage natural and legal persons, and groups, to protect nature, and shall promote respect for all the elements that make up an ecosystem (Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador, 2008).

- **Article 408.-** The State shall guarantee that the mechanisms of production, consumption, and use of natural resources and energy preserve and recover natural cycles and allow for living conditions with dignity.

When speaking of development, the Constitution of Ecuador sets forth its general principles by asserting that the development regime is the organized, sustainable and dynamic set of economic, political, socio-cultural and environmental systems, which guarantee the realization of good living, of *sumak kawsay*. Good living will require that individuals, communities, peoples and nationalities effectively enjoy their rights, and exercise responsibilities within the framework of interculturality, respect for their diversities, and harmonious coexistence with nature.

Article 283.- The economic system is social and solidary; it recognizes the human being as subject and end; it tends to a dynamic and balanced relationship between society, the State and the market, in harmony with nature; and its objective is to guarantee the production and reproduction of the material and immaterial conditions that make good living possible.

3.2. National Development Plan

Another of the vital documents to understand how public policy is built is the National Development Plan that is proposed by the government of the day to present to society its main axes of work and what its objectives and goals would be. The current National Development Plan is designed for 2025, which is the period of validity of the current government. Its most important axes are presented below:

Goal 5: Promote production in a sustainable way by improving productivity levels

- **Policy 5.2** Strengthen agri-food systems and innovative practices that promote environmental sustainability
- **Strategies:**
 - Provide infrastructure, irrigation, legalization of land tenure, technical assistance and training, and research for agricultural, livestock and forestry genetic improvement.

- Develop the practice and productive improvement in a diversified, sustainable and resilient way, which includes good agricultural and intercultural practices, preserve biodiversity and increase the participation of young people and women.
- Facilitate access to specialized financing and insurance depending on the type of crop and innovative activities.

Goal 7: Safeguard the responsible use of natural resources with an environmentally sustainable environment

- **Policy 7.2** Guarantee the efficient management of non-renewable natural resources, through the use of sustainable technologies, which allow the optimization of national production of hydrocarbons, and other activities in the sector's value chain, with social and environmental responsibility
- **Strategies:**
 - Promote the development of public and private investment projects; as well as the use of sustainable technologies in the value chain of the hydrocarbons sector, strengthening the legal framework that allows their execution.
- **Policy 7.3** Strengthen the responsible development of the mining sector through comprehensive strategies that involve environmental and social sustainability and promote the country's economic growth
- **Strategies:**
 - Develop the mining sector by promoting the attraction of national and foreign investment with an environmental focus and strengthening the regulatory framework for the administration, regulation and control of mining activities by the State (Secretaría Nacional de Planificación, 2024).

3.3. Laws

3.3.1. Organic Law on Inclusive Circular Economy (LOECI)

The Organic Law on Inclusive Circular Economy (LOECI) was approved by the National Assembly of Ecuador and published in the Official Gazette Supplement 488 on July 6, 2021. Its main objective is to move from a linear to a circular economic model, promoting the reduction, reuse and recycling of materials, with an inclusive and sustainable approach.

The law establishes a legal framework to promote the circular economy, defining key principles such as extended producer responsibility, efficiency in the use of resources, the inclusion of

grassroots recyclers and waste recovery (LOECI, 2021 art. 3). In addition, it promotes environmental education, eco-design and clean production.

It applies to all natural and legal persons in Ecuadorian territory, including private companies, public institutions, communes, communities, peoples and nationalities (LOECI, 2021 art. 2).

The National System of Inclusive Circular Economy is created, led by the ministries responsible for industrial and environmental policy, which must implement the National Strategy for the Inclusive Circular Economy (ENECE) and coordinate with the decentralized autonomous governments (LOECI, 2021 art. 6-7).

Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)

Producers must manage their products throughout their life cycle, from design to final disposal. Priority is given to the collection and recovery of products with a high environmental impact, such as plastics, electronics and textiles (LOECI, 2021 arts. 19-23).

Sustainable production and consumption

The law promotes:

- **Ecodesign:** Development of products with lower environmental impact and longer useful life (LOECI, 2021 art. 27).
- **Responsible Consumption:** Incentives for Consumers to Adopt Circular Practices (LOECI, 2021 art. 29).
- **Waste Management:** Source Separation and Inclusive Recycling Systems (LOECI, 2021 art. 33).

Inclusion of grassroots recyclers

The work of grassroots recyclers is recognized as a fundamental pillar of the circular economy, promoting their formalization, training and access to financing (LOECI, 2021 art. 15-16).

Incentives and financing

Tax benefits, lines of credit and environmental seals are established for companies that adopt circular economy practices (LOECI, 2021 art. 47).

3.3.2. Law to Prevent and Reduce Food Loss and Waste and Mitigate Hunger in People in Situations of Food Vulnerability

The Law to Prevent and Reduce Food Loss and Waste and Mitigate Hunger aims to establish a regulatory framework to reduce food loss and waste in Ecuador, promoting the redistribution

of food to people in vulnerable situations and encouraging sustainable practices in the food chain.

This law seeks:

- **Reduce food loss and waste** throughout the production chain, from production to final consumption.
- **Facilitate the redistribution of food suitable for consumption** to vulnerable sectors.
- **To promote responsible production and consumption** in the agricultural, commercial and industrial sectors.
- **Promote education and awareness** about food waste and its environmental impact.

The principles of the law include food safety, sustainability, co-responsibility and circular economy (Ley para Prevenir y Reducir la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos y Mitigar el Hambre de las Personas en Situación de Vulnerabilidad Alimentaria, 2022 Art. 4).

The regulation applies to food producers, distributors, marketers and consumers, including public and private institutions involved in the food production and distribution chain (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 5).

Institutionality and implementation mechanisms

- The National System for the Reduction of Food Loss and Waste is created, coordinated by the Ministries of Agriculture, Health and Environment (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 7).
- Mechanisms are established for control, monitoring and promotion of good practices, including the implementation of collection centers and food banks (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 9).

Incentives and obligations

- Tax and financial incentives are granted to companies that take steps to reduce food waste (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 12).
- Food donations are regulated to ensure proper handling and safe redistribution (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 15).
- Supermarkets and restaurants are obliged to promote food use practices (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 18).

Sanctions and control

Failure to comply with the law entails administrative and economic sanctions, depending on the degree of infraction (Ley para la Pérdida y el Desperdicio de Alimentos, 2022 Art. 22).

3.4. Public Institutions

3.4.1. Ministry of Environment, Water, and Ecological Transition (MAATE)

The purpose of MAATE is "To guarantee the quality, conservation and sustainability of natural resources, through the effective exercise of stewardship, planning, regulation, control, coordination and management of the environment and water resources, through the participation of public, private, community organizations and citizens, within the framework of respect, integrity, responsibility and transparency." (Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica, 2023). This governing institution is in charge of several programs and projects, framed in these purposes:

➤ **GENDER AND CLIMATE CHANGE ECUADOR Action Plan**

Ecuador's Gender and Climate Change Action Plan (PAGCC) is a public policy instrument designed to integrate the gender perspective into climate change adaptation and mitigation actions in the country. Led by the Undersecretariat of Climate Change of the Ministry of the Environment, Water and Ecological Transition (MAATE), the PAGCC has the technical support of the National Council for Gender Equality (CNIG) and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN).

Mission: To guide the implementation of multi-stakeholder and multi-level actions to contribute to the reduction of gender gaps within the framework of the implementation of Ecuador's First NDC, strengthening climate change management through a comprehensive public policy that promotes benefits for women, with an emphasis on indigenous, Afro-descendants, Montuvias and LGBTIQ+ people. (Ministry of the Environment, Water and Ecological Transition, 2024)

The PAGcc is implemented in two phases: short-term (2020-2025) in line with the First Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) and medium-term (2025-2030) with the Second NDC. Tools such as the Measurement, Reporting and Verification System (MRV) have been developed to evaluate its effectiveness and ensure the mainstreaming of the gender approach in the country's climate policies.

Ecuador's Gender and Climate Change Action Plan (PAGcc-Ecuador 2024) establishes a series of public policies aimed at integrating the gender approach into the country's climate action. Concisely, the main policies are:

- **Research with a gender focus**

- Development of gender-disaggregated climate information.
- Studies on differentiated impacts of climate change on women and men (Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica, 2024)
- **Gender equality policies in climate action**
 - Incorporation of the gender approach in climate mitigation and adaptation plans, programmes and projects.
 - Creation and strengthening of regulations to guarantee equity in decision-making on climate change.
- **Capacity building**
 - Training programs in climate leadership with a gender perspective.
 - Training on climate adaptation and mitigation issues for women and vulnerable groups.
- **Technological development for climate resilience**
 - Promotion of sustainable technologies that reduce gender gaps.
 - Supporting Women-Led Initiatives in the Environmental Sector (Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica, 2024).
- **Communication and awareness**
 - Education and dissemination strategies on gender and climate change.
 - Campaigns to make visible the role of women in climate conservation and mitigation (Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica, 2024)

➤ **National Strategy for Inclusive Circular Economy (ENECI)**

The National Strategy for Inclusive Circular Economy (ENECI) is a plan promoted by the Ministry of Production, Foreign Trade, Investment and Fisheries and the Ministry of the Environment, Water and Ecological Transition, with the support of the European Union. Its main objective is to transform Ecuador's economic model, moving from a linear economy (based on the extraction, production and disposal of materials) to a circular economy that promotes sustainability, waste reduction and the optimization of the use of natural resources.

The general objective of the National Strategy for the Inclusive Circular Economy is to promote economic development that does not depend on the irrational use of natural resources, promoting business competitiveness through an inclusive, regenerative circular economy with a sustainable territorial approach. Specific objectives include implementing sustainable strategies, improving material use efficiency, promoting sectoral partnerships, and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. (Ministerio de Producción, Comercio Exterior, Inversiones y Pesca, & Ministerio del Ambiente, Agua y Transición Ecológica, 2024)

Public policies proposed in the ENECI

1. **Strengthening the regulatory framework:** Implementation of laws and regulations to promote the circular economy and sustainable waste management.
2. **Economic incentives:** Creation of financing mechanisms and tax benefits for companies that adopt circular practices.
3. **Extended producer responsibility (EPR):** Obligation for companies to manage the life cycle of their products, promoting their recycling and reuse.
4. **Integrating the circular economy into urban planning:** Fostering sustainable cities through the reuse of materials and reducing waste.
5. **Promotion of education and awareness:** Development of training and awareness programmes on the importance of the circular economy in society.

3.5. Recent Conflicts in Public Policy

Public policies in Ecuador are aligned with progressive principles of sustainability and ecological rights, however, there are challenges to their implementation. In the non-renewable resource sectors, such as oil and mining, although sustainability is promoted, these activities often carry environmental and social risks. The balance between economic development and nature protection remains a considerable challenge. As for the agri-food sector, although policies seek to promote innovative and sustainable practices, it is necessary to strengthen infrastructure and ensure that small producers can access the benefits of these programs, especially in rural and hard-to-reach areas. The analysis of Ecuador's public policies cannot be carried out without addressing two recent events that have had a significant impact on the country: the energy crisis of 2024 and the Yasuní ITT popular consultation. Both events are intertwined with the fundamental principles of sustainable development and environmental protection embodied in the Constitution of Ecuador and its National Development Plan.

Another crucial event on Ecuador's political agenda is the popular consultation of August 20, 2023, in which 59% of voters decided to end oil exploitation in Block 43-ITT, located in the Yasuni National Park. This area, one of the most biodiverse in the world, has been the center of controversy for years due to the environmental and social impacts of oil exploitation, directly affecting indigenous peoples in voluntary isolation such as the Tagaeri and Taromenane (Astudillo, 2024).

Despite this historic victory for environmentalists, the process of shutting down oil wells has been slow and complex. As of October 2024, only five of the 247 wells in Yasuni have been shut down, and the government has announced that all of the wells will not be shut down until 2029.

This delay is due to economic considerations: the immediate abandonment of Block 43-ITT would imply significant losses for the Ecuadorian economy, which depends largely on oil revenues (Vásconez, 2024).

President Daniel Noboa faces a difficult dilemma. On the one hand, there is the mandate of the popular consultation, which demands an end to oil exploitation to protect one of the most fragile ecosystems in the world. On the other hand, there is the need to stabilize the country's public finances, which depend largely on oil revenues. The government has unveiled a plan that includes phasing down the wells through 2029, costing more than \$1.3 billion in studies, infrastructure dismantling and environmental repairs.

The Yasuni consultation and the energy crisis are not isolated events; rather, they reflect the tensions inherent in Ecuador's public policies around economic development and environmental sustainability. The country faces heavy dependence on oil for its tax revenues, while its energy systems urgently require modernization and diversification to ensure cleaner and more stable energy production.

Recurrent failures in hydropower infrastructure underscore the need to move towards a more robust system that incorporates renewable energy sources. At the same time, the exit of the oil sector from Yasuní highlights the need to reimagine Ecuador's economic model, betting on sectors that respect the principles of environmental sustainability established in the Constitution.

We can say that, despite the fact that the Ecuadorian Constitution incorporates laws for the protection of nature and principles of sustainability, such as the Sumak Kawsay, there is an obvious contradiction with the policies implemented by the current governments, which seek to promote a "development of good living". Ecuador's current context reflects the challenges of balancing economic development with environmental sustainability, a common challenge in countries with high dependence on their natural resources. Examples of these tensions can be seen in the energy crisis and the popular consultation on the Yasuní ITT, both cases that illustrate the dilemma between promoting development and conserving the environment. To build a sustainable future, Ecuador will need to make bold decisions that prioritize diversifying its economy and energy sources, while protecting its invaluable natural wealth.

4. Methodology

The research developed by the ToBe Ecuador team adopts a qualitative, exploratory, and interpretative approach, aimed at generating situated knowledge on sustainable wellbeing as understood and practiced by Indigenous and rural communities in Ecuador. This approach is consistent with the broader objectives of the ToBe project, particularly in fostering epistemic

pluralism and grounding policy-oriented indicators in the lived experiences and values of local actors.

The study follows a multiple case study design, focusing on four community-based organizations located in two contrasting regions: the Andean highlands (UNORCAC and UNCISA in the province of Imbabura) and the Amazonian lowlands (Sumak Yaku and the Kallari Association in the province of Napo). These cases were selected based on their territorial relevance, organizational consolidation, and commitment to alternative development practices aligned with the principles of Buen Vivir (*Sumak Kawsay*).

Data collection was carried out through a combination of qualitative methods, including:

- **Semi-structured interviews** with community leaders, organizational members, and institutional stakeholders. These interviews allowed for an in-depth understanding of local perspectives on wellbeing, sustainability, and technology, as well as perceptions regarding public policy and institutional support.
- **Participant observation** during field visits, community workshops, and organizational meetings. This technique provided contextual insights into daily practices, decision-making processes, and socio-environmental dynamics within the communities.
- **Document and literature review**, including legal frameworks, institutional reports, and academic studies related to sustainable development, Indigenous rights, and post-development paradigms. This helped to triangulate field data and to situate the findings within a broader analytical framework.

The research process was guided by ethical considerations centered on reciprocity, respect, and active listening. Prior informed consent was obtained for all interviews and visits, and feedback sessions were held with the participating communities to share preliminary findings and validate interpretations.

The methodological design emphasized co-construction of knowledge and reflexivity, recognizing community members not merely as subjects of research but as active participants and knowledge holders. This perspective strengthens the legitimacy and applicability of the findings and ensures that they contribute meaningfully to the development of context-sensitive and transformative indicators within the ToBe project.

Table 3. Details of interviews conducted in the field

Imbabura Cases				
Encodings		Organization	Place	Charge
Interviewee 1	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Arrayanes	President of the Arrayanes community
Interviewee 2	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Cuicocha	President of the Cuicocha community

Interviewee 3	Organization 1	UNORCAC	UNORCAC Office	President of UNORCAC
Interviewee 4	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Piñan	President of the Piñan community
Interviewee 5	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Cercado	President of the El Cercado community
Interviewee 6	Organization 1-SM	UNORCAC	Sumak Mikuy	Manager Sumak Mikuy
Interviewee 7	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Piñan	Community Teachers
Interviewee 8	Organization 1	UNORCAC	Piñan	Community Member
Interviewee 9	Organization 2	Sumak Yaku	Sumak Yaku	Secretary
Interviewee 10	Organization 2	Sumak Yaku	Sumak Yaku	President Sumak Yaku
Interviewee 11	Organization 2	Sumak Yaku	Sumak Yaku	Operators
Interviewee 12	Organization 2	Sumak Yaku	Sumak Yaku	Assembly Members
Interviewee 13	Organization 2	Sumak Yaku	Sumak Yaku	Representative
Interviewee 14	Organization 3	UNCISA	Asociación ReyMola Cocha	Representative
Interviewee 15	Organization 3	UNCISA	Asociación Tatora Sisa	Artisan
Interviewee 16	Organization 3	UNCISA	Huaycopungo	President of Huaycopungo
Interviewee 17	Organization 3	UNCISA	Huaycopungo	Worker of Huaycopungo
Interviewee 18	Organization 3	UNCISA	Cuatro Esquinas	Representative
Interviewee 19	Organization 3	UNCISA	UNCISA	Representative
Interviewee 20	Organization 3	UNCISA	Urku Wasi	Representative
Interviewee 21	Organization 3	UNCISA	Balcón del Lago Cabins	Representative
Stakeholders				
Encodings		Organization	Place	Charge
Interviewee 22	Organization 4	Ministry of Environment, Water and Ecological Transition	Online Interview	Director of Sustainable Production and Development
Interviewee 23	Organization 5	Ministry of Finance	Online Interview	Former Minister
Interviewee 24	Organization 6	Latin American Mining Organization (OLAMI)	Online Interview	Director
Interviewee 25	Organization 7	Yachay University	Online Interview	Rector
Interviewee 26	Organization 8	KISTH Foundation	Online Interview	Vicepresident
Interviewee 27-01 y Interviewee 27-02	Organization 9	Municipality of Cotacachi	Online Interview	27-01 Director of Economic Development and Tourism; 27-02 Manager of the Public

				Company of Renewable Energy and Tourism
Amazon case				
Interviewee	Encodings	Organization	Place	Charge
Interviewee 28	Organization 10	Kallari	Online Interview	President of Kallari
Interviewee 29	Organization 10	Kallari	Online Interview	Administrador Kallari
Interviewee 30	Organization 10	Kallari	Kallari Offices	Producing partner
Interviewee 31-01 and Interviewee 31-02	Organization 10	Kallari	Kaparik Urku Entrepreneurship	31-01 Producing partner 31-02 Producing partner

Own elaboration

4.1. Study Cases

Building on the methodological approach described above, this section presents the four case studies selected for in-depth analysis. These cases illustrate diverse territorial, cultural, and organizational configurations that offer rich insights into the situated understandings and practices of sustainable wellbeing in Ecuador. The selected cases—UNORCAC, UNCISA, and Sumak Yaku in the Andean region of Imbabura, and the Kallari Association in the Amazonian province of Napo—were chosen not only for their geographical and ecological representativeness, but also for their long-standing commitment to community organization, socio-environmental stewardship, and alternative development strategies. Each case study is presented through a narrative that integrates contextual information, key organizational features, and thematic findings derived from interviews, observations, and document review. Together, these cases contribute to a nuanced understanding of the conditions, challenges, and opportunities for sustainable wellbeing in Indigenous territories, and provide valuable empirical grounding for the formulation of transformative indicators within the ToBe project.

4.1.1. Union of Peasant Organizations of Cotacachi (UNORCAC)

UNORCAC is a second-degree non-profit organization, made up of forty-eight communities together with various indigenous and mestizo peasant grassroots organizations, located in the Andean area of the Cotacachi Canton, Imbabura Province. Created in April 1977, after a socio-organizational process led by a group of young indigenous intellectuals from Cotacachi. The conditions of discrimination and poverty in which the majority of the indigenous peasant

population of the area lived and the decision to reverse this situation were the motivations to achieve the unity of the communes and initiate the struggle.

From UNORCAC's perspective, they are in an Alli Kawsay within the constitution of the organization, and it is what guides the community authorities. This means living in harmony within communities, decisions based on ethics and morals, and spiritual acts to seek peace and harmony. In their understanding, the Sumak Kawsay is much bigger, it is the final goal but the process is still underway, they would achieve it by living in peace without having any more "desires" and being content with life, it is full satisfaction where one of their most important resources is clean water.

There is a constant struggle for food sovereignty through access to water and land, the conservation of biodiversity, the promotion of agricultural production and other productive, sustainable, and sustainable alternatives and the fair marketing of their products. Since education and health are fundamental rights, access is demanded for all communities and innovative proposals are generated with an intercultural approach. UNORCAC is committed to achieving the broadest and most conscious participation of peasants and indigenous people in the construction of a more just and equitable society for both men and women.

In its initiatives, UNORCAC advocates for egalitarian development with identity, benefit for all communities equally, economic development with more reforestation projects, alternatives to extractive development projects since they do not agree with the environmental impacts generated by mines and their main concern is water. Agriculture is an important part of these alternatives, for example, through Sumak Mikuy they try to achieve economic development in an ecological way. Economic development is sought through the expansion of Sumak Mikuy where the vision is to have an industrialization process and increase the number of production plants to ten. In addition, community association is important as social sustainability because thanks to that decisions are made in a participatory way. Caring for nature is an important principle in all projects, as well as sustainability with the "caring for Pachamama".

Principles and objectives

1. Egalitarian development with identity, benefit all communities.
2. Reforestation projects, alternatives to extractive development projects to protect water.
3. Agriculture is a big part of these alternatives, for example, through Sumak Mikuy they try to obtain economic development in an ecological way. Economic development is sought through the expansion of Sumak Mikuy, the vision is to have an industrialization process and increase the number of production plants to ten.
4. Community association as social sustainability: decisions made in a participatory way.

5. Caring for nature is an important principle in all projects: sustainability and caring for Pachamama.
6. Raising awareness of organic agricultural production.

4.1.2. Union of Indigenous Communities of San Rafael (UNCISA)

The Union of Indigenous Communities of San Rafael is constituted in the Otavalo people, in the parish of San Rafael de la Laguna, Otavalo Canton, Province of Imbabura. UNCISA was founded in 1999 and since then has ensured the well-being of its nine communities including the parish center, such as: Tocagon, Capilla Pamba, Huaycopungo, Cachiviro, Cachimuel, Cuatro Esquinas, San Miguel Alto, San Miguel Bajo, Mushuk Ñan. UNCISA is in charge of resolving situations and cases of various kinds that sometimes the councils are unable to solve, as well as contributing to the development and social, economic and cultural improvement of their communities.

In UNCISA, development is understood as the progress of communities where the authorities work for the benefit of the population, both economically and culturally. Sustainability is essential for any activity to be sustained in the long term. For UNICSA, Good Living and Sumak Yaku is reflected in education, health and all the basic fields necessary to achieve progress or development. They emphasize that the environment is currently feeling the effect of climate change, so caring for the environment must begin at home, then in schools and colleges, to achieve organic awareness and preserve this environment. In the communities they feel the effects of the contamination of hotels with sewage and garbage since they do not have adequate treatment plants, they do not work well. They say that in the high areas they have more control, the hotels in the lower areas are the ones that pollute the most, in addition the boats spill motor oil into the lake, it is something they constantly fight for

Its main initiatives are evidenced by avoiding legal processes and the costs that would entail since all problems are solved within the territory and as a community. In some cases, indigenous justice is applied and a dignified reintegration of those involved into the community is achieved. They are also constantly looking for projects for the benefit of the communities and the parish. In their activities, they always seek security for the inhabitants through agreements with the national police. In addition, they seek to promote programs for the protection and conservation of the environment and biodiversity of ancestral and spiritual areas with practices specific to the community, to maintain and expand relations of solidarity

and coordination with other organizations and communities that develop similar activities at the local, regional and national levels in order to establish mechanisms of cultural support, technical and scientific. To contribute to all activities in the area in favor of the unity and strengthening of the communities affiliated to UNCISA.

Principles and objectives:

- Avoid legal proceedings, problems are solved within the territory.
- Indigenous justice is applied and a dignified reintegration of those involved in the community is possible.
- To seek projects for the benefit of the communities and the parish.
- Security for the inhabitants through agreements with the National Police.
- Have an adequate cemetery.
- Longhouse in good condition.
- Good leaders for the parish council and municipal councils to manage communities well.
- To show oneself as an example for the next generations.

4.1.3. Potable Water Administrative Board SUMAK YAKU

In 2004, the Sumak Yaku Drinking Water Administrative Board was formed with the communities of Araque, Camuendo, La Compañía Baja, La Compañía Alta, Arias Ucu, Yacu Pata, Agato, and Quinchuquí. Sumak Yaku is a small public sector company, dedicated to the provision of drinking water services, with self-financing capital. They offer quality drinking water service to the users of the eight communities belonging to their jurisdiction, taking care of the environment, efficiently using resources and strengthening the union and trust of the community.

In this organization, Buen Vivir and Sumak Kawsay is always a principle in the work. The principles are to work without stealing or lying. The work is carried out with a sense of responsibility towards the community, as well as environmental sustainability with a holistic understanding: without a healthy environment in the mountains there is no water, and without water you do not live well.

With respect to their initiatives, they have a social focus mainly towards access to water and communal services with the idea that users pay and want to give something significant in return with an extra; for example, operators and other staff members make small Christmas

bags with items to give to users. In addition, they work for a lower price of water, and different rates depending on needs. They seek contributions to communities through projects with environmental sustainability as a fundamental principle guided by two objectives: a) to protect water tanks and pool areas by keeping them clean (through monthly cleanings and mingas); b) take care of the mountain environment (moors where the water comes from) since plants and trees are needed as filters for the water. Sumak Yaku helps with the conservation and reforestation of native trees that function as filters. The area has many non-native trees (e.g. eucalyptus trees that take in a lot of water, but do not release it). They work with scientists and ecologists on this and seek to raise awareness about sustainable agricultural practices and raise awareness of the use of water with its natural origin, constantly working on its conservation.

Principles and objectives:

- Access to water and communal services.
- Reduced water prices, and different rates depending on needs.
- Contributions to communities through projects.
- Environmental sustainability in two parts: i) protecting water tanks and water pool areas by keeping them clean (through monthly cleanings and mingas). ii) To take care of the mountain environment (páramos).
- Conservation and reforestation of native trees that function as water filters.
- Work with scientists and environmentalists to raise awareness about sustainable farming practices (no burning, for example).
- Encourage water conservation.
- To remain a self-sufficient company that provides access to water to increasingly wide users.
- State-of-the-art automatic technological installations for water pumping.
- The user's payment will be facilitated by the creation of payment points in the communities.
- Digitization of data management systems, data collection of pipelines, their locations and users to digitize.

4.1.4. Kallari Association

The Kallari Association is a community organization made up mainly of Kichwa families from the Amazon region of Ecuador, in the province of Napo. Founded in December 2003, it brings together around 850 producers from 21 communities in the Tena canton. Kallari is dedicated

to the production, processing and marketing of agricultural products such as cocoa, guayusa and vanilla, with a focus on sustainability and respect for traditional practices.

The association works under the "Amazon chakra" system, a diversified agricultural method that respects the natural environment, fosters biodiversity and contributes to food self-sufficiency. This system ensures that the products are grown without monoculture techniques, promoting a balance with the ecosystem.

Products they offer:

- Cocoa beans, cocoa nibs, cocoa paste or liquor, cocoa butter, cocoa powder and chocolates.
- Natural vanilla beans and natural vanilla powder.
- Dehydrated guayusa leaves, crushed guayusa and guayusa powder.
- Guided tours of Kallari's facilities, communities and farmers' farms.
- Handicrafts and souvenirs.

Principles and objectives:

- Promote integral well-being, which includes economic development, health, food and respect for nature.
- Maintain biodiversity through an "Amazon chakra" system that ensures agricultural production in harmony with the ecosystem.
- To transmit ancestral knowledge and Kichwa cultural values to the new generations, strengthening the identity of the community.
- Eliminate intermediaries to obtain fair prices and increase the direct income of producers through fair trade.
- Train young people in sustainable agricultural techniques, stewardship and product development, ensuring the continuity of the partnership.
- Produce and market cocoa, vanilla and guayusa derivatives with added value, accessing international markets to strengthen the economy of the community.

4.2. Field Visits

The ToBe project team in Ecuador carried out a series of field trips in December 2023 with the purpose of establishing direct relationships and getting to know in depth the realities of various communities. These visits allowed them to interact with local leaders and members of key organizations, in addition to observing the cultural and productive dynamics in each territory. In collaboration with entities such as UNORCAC and UNCISA, the team not only identified the specific needs of each community, but also generated spaces for dialogue aimed at building sustainable solutions and strengthening shared knowledge. The fieldwork carried

out is detailed below, including the meetings and activities that laid the foundations for mutual support over time.

4.2.1. UNORCAC

The Ecuador team of the ToBe project made a first contact with this organization in December 2023, with field interviews, getting to know the territory and talking with its main leaders within each community. In this exercise, the needs of the different communities and the organization's leadership were made visible, so, inspired by a reciprocal way of giving back to the community in ways other than leaving an economic amount, meetings were held with the directors of UNORCAC to discuss these needs and contribute from knowledge, generating a positive impact on them.

Day 1: December 9

- *Cotacahi* municipality: interview with municipal authorities.
- *Ashambuela* Community, talk with representatives of the community, recognition of the place, visit to their crops and community house.

Day 2: December 10

- “*La Pachamama nos alimenta*” market: observation of the more than 80 different products and the way they are marketed by partners of the communities affiliated to UNORCAC.
- *Cuicocha* lagoon: known as lagoon of the Gods or *TsuiCocha* and of crater origin. The particularity of this of this lagoon is that in its center are located two islets. Observation of flora and fauna.
- *Ruta Sagrada*: located along the *Cuicocha* lagoon, walked along the trail with a wise member of the community.
- *Cercado* community: one of the biggest communities in UNORCAC, interview with the president and visit to the community school.

Day 3: December 11

- *Piñan* community: observation of flora and fauna, visit to the community school, interview with schoolteachers, interview with the president of the community and visit to the community of *Guananí*.

Day 4: December 12

- *Arrayanes* community: observation of community crops, interview with the community president.
- *Sumak Mikuy*: community agro-enterprise, organic dry fruits, observation of the site, production process and interview with the representative.
- UNORCAC office: closing of field visits, interview with president of UNORCAC.

Figure 8. Image set: Field visit to UNORCAC

4.2.2. UNCISA

On the first visit to UNCISA in December 2023, the team carried out various activities to learn about the cultural and productive dynamics of local communities. They began with a visit to the central fair of Otavalo, observing indigenous handicrafts, and in the UNCISA office they participated in an introductory talk and in the observation of the work with reeds.

In Tocagón, they explored artisanal work with totora reeds and visited the Urku Wasi and Balcón del Lago enterprises, interviewing artisans and members of UNCISA. In Huayaopungo, they observed the tourist site and interviewed the president and community workers. They also visited Cuatro Esquinas, where they observed the cultivation of and interviewed their representatives, and in Cachiviro they visited the Rey Mola Cocha association to learn about its activities.

Field visits

Day 1: December 16

- *Otavalo* central fair: visit and observation of indigenous handicrafts
- *UNCISA* office: introductory talk, visit and observation of *totora*.
- *Tocagón* community: observation of *totora* handicrafts, visit to local enterprises Urku Wasi and Balcón del lago, interview with artisans and members of UNCISA.

Day 2: December 17

- *Huayaopungo* community: observation tourist site, interview with de president and workers.
- *Cuatro esquinas* community: observation of *chochos*, interview with the representatives.
- *Cachiviro* community: visit at the *Rey Mola Cocha* association and interview.

Figure 9. Image set: Field visit to UNCISA

4.2.3. Sumak Yaku

The first approach in Sumak Yaku was carried out in December 2023, where there was a visit and observation of the place, observation of the processes of water storage and distribution, conversation with operators, interviews with members of the board and observation of a community assembly.

Field visits

Day 1 and day: December 14-15

- *Sumak Yaku* co-operative: visit and observation of the place, observation of water processes, talk with operators, interviews, and observation of the community assembly.

Figure 10. Image set: Field visit to SUMAK YAKU

4.2.4. Kallari Association

As part of the activities carried out in 2024, an initial meeting was held with the Kallari Association, which provided the opportunity to establish contact with the organization’s leadership team. Following this preliminary engagement, an online interview was scheduled and conducted on July 15, 2024, during which valuable insights were gathered from both the president and the administrator of the association. Subsequently, on July 26, 2024, a field visit was conducted to deepen the understanding of Kallari’s work, engage directly with its producer members, and observe the functioning of its offices and core activities.

Field Visit – Day 1: July 26, 2024

- Kallari Offices: Meeting with the president of the Kallari Association, guided tour of the offices in Tena, and interview with a female producer member.
- Kaparik Urku: Introductory talk and guided visit to this community-based tourism initiative; observation of cultivated plots using the traditional Chakra agroforestry method; and demonstration of artisan techniques and value-added cacao products. Interviews were conducted with the founders of the Kaparik Urku initiative.

Figure 11. Image set: Field visit to Kallari

The ToBe Ecuador project team made an extensive tour of various communities in Ecuador in 2023 and 2024, allowing them to learn about the cultural, productive, and organizational dynamics of each place. Through interviews with local leaders, visits to key sites and direct observation of community activities, the team was able to identify the particular needs of each community and establish an open dialogue with UNORCAC and other entities. This approach made it possible to lay the foundations for reciprocal support, aimed not only at an economic contribution, but also at the exchange of knowledge that seeks to generate a positive and sustainable impact in each of the communities involved.

5. Results

5.1. Barriers

In the analysis of the community organizations and indigenous associations of the cases studied, various barriers and drivers were identified that directly influence their development, sustainability, and capacity for growth. The barriers encompass structural, financial, cultural, and infrastructural challenges that limit the opportunities for these organizations to achieve their goals and meet the needs of their communities. These obstacles are reinforced by a lack

of institutional support and resistance to certain changes, which complicates the adoption of new practices and technologies that could modernize their activities.

On the other hand, there are driving factors that allow these organizations to move forward amid these limitations. These drivers include a strong sense of cultural identity, commitment to sustainable development, and active collaboration of its members. These core values not only help preserve ancestral knowledge and traditional practices but also boost entrepreneurship through activities such as community-based tourism and the diversification of value-added products. In addition, community leadership and interest in the education and training of young people are key aspects that contribute to the resilience and continuity of these organizations.

The main barriers and drivers identified in the case studies are presented below, providing a comprehensive view of the challenges and opportunities faced by these communities in their pursuit of equitable and sustainable development.

Table 4. Comparative analysis of barriers between Imbabura and Amazonia cases

Barriers	Imbabura			Amazon
Category	UNORCAC	Sumac Yaku	UNCISA	Kallari
Economic	Lack of financing and limited access to markets.	External financial dependence; limitations in municipal resources.	Dependency on family credits; limited economic diversification.	External financial dependence; difficulties in exporting local products.
Social	Youth migration; Community disinterest.	Community resistance to change; labor migration.	Family migration; resistance to change.	Youth migration; cultural resistance to change.
Cultural	Kichwa loss and traditions due to external influences.	Loss of cultural identity due to the replacement of traditional practices by modern machinery.	Loss of ancestral practices; there is a lack of intergenerational transmission.	Risk loss of ancestral knowledge due to limited generational transmission.
Infrastructure	Poor condition of roads; lack of tourism infrastructure.	High need, maintenance, water infrastructure and meter renovation.	There is a lack of tourist signage; deficiencies in basic services.	Deficient road infrastructure, hindering mobility and commerce.
Institutional	There is a lack of public policies and insufficient state support.	Scarce institutional recognition in conservation of natural resources.	Centralization of resources; there is a lack of local institutional collaboration.	Limited institutional support and complex regulations (mandatory e-invoicing).

Own elaboration

The comparative analysis of the barriers identified in the case studies of Imbabura (UNORCAC, Sumak Yaku, UNCISA) and Amazonia (Kallari) reveals a set of common structural challenges, although they manifest themselves in a differentiated way according to the territorial, cultural and organizational particularities of each context. The barriers have been grouped into five dimensions: economic, social, cultural, infrastructural and institutional.

Economic barriers

In both regions, organizations face significant constraints in achieving financial autonomy and stable market access. In the case of UNORCAC, there is a limited availability of financing and difficulties in accessing marketing channels. Similarly, Sumak Yaku identifies a heavy reliance on external financial resources and budgetary constraints at the municipal level. For its part, UNCISA faces a situation of economic dependence on family credits, with little productive diversification. In the Amazon, Kallari also experiences a high dependence on external financing, aggravated by the complexity of the processes of exporting local products. These barriers show a common pattern of economic fragility that limits the possibilities of long-term sustainability.

Social barriers

Current social transformations, particularly around migration and generational involvement, constitute a cross-cutting obstacle in both contexts. In Imbabura, both UNORCAC and Sumak Yaku identify youth migration as a phenomenon that weakens the continuity of organizational processes, along with resistance to change by communities. At UNCISA, this barrier extends to the family sphere, revealing a pattern of collective migration and difficulties in adapting to new dynamics. In the Amazon, interviewees linked to Kallari also highlight youth migration and cultural resistance to transformation as factors that threaten cohesion and generational renewal. These elements compromise the social sustainability of community projects and their ability to adapt to changing contexts.

Cultural barriers

Cultural barriers are closely linked to the loss of ancestral knowledge, the transformation of traditional practices and the fragmentation of cultural identity. In Imbabura, UNORCAC reports the progressive loss of Kichwa traditions due to external influences, while Sumak Yaku points to the replacement of ancestral practices with modern technologies, which weakens the links with the territory and with traditional ecological knowledge. UNCISA emphasizes the break in the intergenerational transmission of cultural practices, a phenomenon also observed in the Amazon. In the latter case, Kallari identifies a high risk of loss of ancestral knowledge as a result of limited transmission between generations. This

situation stresses the processes of identity strengthening and delegitimizes non-hegemonic forms of knowledge.

Infrastructure barriers

In terms of infrastructure, the limitations observed directly affect mobility, access to basic services and connection with markets. In Imbabura, UNORCAC reports the poor state of the roads and the lack of tourist infrastructure, while Sumak Yaku emphasizes the shortcomings in water infrastructure, as well as maintenance and renovation needs. In the case of UNCISA, the lack of tourist signage and deficiencies in essential services are pointed out. In the Amazon, Kallari faces a precarious road infrastructure, which represents an obstacle to both the circulation of products and the connection between communities. These conditions hinder local economic development and reduce opportunities for productive diversification.

Institutional barriers

Finally, institutional barriers express a pattern of weak articulation between community organizations and the State. In Imbabura, limitations are identified such as the scarce presence of public policies, the centralization of resources and the lack of inter-institutional collaboration. Sumak Yaku, for example, points to the lack of institutional recognition in the conservation of natural resources, which weakens the legitimacy of their actions. In the Amazon, Kallari shows not only a lack of institutional support, but also the presence of complex regulations (such as mandatory electronic invoicing) that make it difficult to market community products. These institutional barriers limit the ability of organizations to scale their processes and generate sustainable transformations on a larger scale.

Conclusion

The analysis of the barriers faced by organizations in Imbabura and the Amazon reveals the existence of common structural conditions that hinder the development of sustainable local initiatives, including financial dependence, loss of cultural knowledge, institutional weakness, and infrastructural fragility. However, these barriers are expressed differently according to the territorial context and organizational trajectory of each case. Addressing these problems requires the strengthening of public policies that recognize the diversity of knowledge, foster territorial autonomy, and promote technical and financial support sensitive to the cultural and ecological context of each region.

5.2. Drivers

Table 5. Comparative analysis of drivers between Imbabura and Amazonia cases

Drivers	Imbabura			Amazon
Category	UNORCAC	Sumak Yaku	UNCISA	Kallari

Economic	Economic diversification, innovative products; financial sustainability (microenterprises).	External financing strategies (NGOs); Expansion of the drinking water service.	Local economic empowerment; expansion of the tourist offer.	Certified productive diversification; elimination of intermediaries by increasing direct revenues.
Social	Strengthening community cohesion, youth inclusion and community networks.	Effective community organization through mingas and job stability community operators.	Family organization and territorial conflict resolution; local collaborative networks.	Community cohesion and active participation of young people/women, direct improvement of community quality of life.
Cultural	Preservation of Kichwa cultural practices, rituals, festivities, promotion of ancestral knowledge.	Preservation of cultural identity through traditional practices and community coexistence (Sumak Kawsay).	Local cultural revitalization and cultural education from an early age.	Preservation of the Amazonian farm system; Intergenerational transmission ancestral knowledge.
Educational	Training in local leadership, transmission of agricultural knowledge and sustainability.	Constant technical training in sustainable water management, maintenance and environmental conservation.	Technical strengthening (training in digital tourism, training of local tour guides and sustainable management).	Specialized training in advanced agricultural techniques and youth leadership.
Environmental	Biodiversity conservation, sustainable agricultural management and climate resilience.	Conservation of water resources, reforestation and environmental awareness for sustainable water management.	Tourism environmental protection; sustainable use of natural resources and destructive mining prevention.	Certified organic agriculture; sustainable practices such as bioles and composting, in balance with nature.

Own elaboration

The analysis of the drivers of well-being reveals how community organizations in Imbabura and the Amazon activate various strategies adapted to their territorial, cultural, and productive contexts. Unlike barriers, drivers represent organizational capacities, territorial knowledge, and collective actions that strengthen the social fabric and promote sustainability. These drivers have been classified into five categories: economic, social, cultural, educational, and environmental.

Economic Drivers

The cases analyzed show a diverse set of strategies to strengthen community economic autonomy. In Imbabura, UNORCAC focuses on productive diversification, the development of innovative products and financial sustainability through micro-enterprises. Sumak Yaku complements this strategy through access to external funding managed by NGOs and the expansion of services such as clean water.

For its part, UNCISA is committed to strengthening local tourism as a way to generate income and boost the community economy. In the Amazon, Kallari presents a certified productive diversification strategy, which seeks to eliminate intermediaries and increase the direct income of producer families. These strategies aim not only to improve economic conditions, but also to consolidate production models compatible with the culture and environment.

Social Drivers

On the social level, the drivers are linked to the construction of social capital, community cohesion and the inclusion of historically marginalized actors. At UNORCAC, we work on strengthening community networks, especially with young people, to ensure organizational sustainability. Sumak Yaku promotes community organization through mingas and job stability for community operators, which builds trust and collective commitment.

UNCISA, on the other hand, stresses the importance of family organization and the resolution of territorial conflicts, as well as articulation with local collaborative networks. In the Amazon, Kallari highlights the active participation of women and young people as a fundamental axis for improving the quality of life and social sustainability. These drivers reflect solid organizational forms that allow development processes to be sustained from the local level.

Cultural Drivers

In all cases, culture is presented as a structuring axis of well-being, through the revitalization of ancestral knowledge, community identity, and ritual practices. At UNORCAC, this is expressed in the promotion of Kichwa culture through festivities and the transmission of ancestral knowledge. Sumak Yaku reinforces this aspect through community coexistence and the use of the concept of *Sumak Kawsay* as an articulating principle of its actions.

UNCISA implements cultural revitalization strategies from an early age, through community education with an intercultural approach. For its part, in the Amazon, Kallari works for the preservation of the Amazonian agricultural system and the intergenerational transmission of ancestral knowledge, as pillars of cultural and territorial sustainability.

Educational Drivers

The educational promoters reflect a common commitment to the strengthening of local capacities and technical training adapted to territorial realities. UNORCAC focuses on local

leadership and the transmission of sustainable agricultural knowledge. Sumak Yaku offers ongoing training in water management and environmental conservation, as part of a resilience strategy.

UNCISA develops technical training processes in digital tourism, community management and tourist guidance, thus contributing to local economic diversification. In the Amazon, Kallari promotes specialized training in advanced agricultural techniques and youth leadership, which strengthens organizational autonomy and promotes innovation processes based on local knowledge.

Environmental Drivers

In the environmental dimension, the cases analyzed show a deep ecological awareness that articulates conservation, sustainable production and climate adaptation. UNORCAC works on biodiversity conservation and sustainable agricultural management, while Sumak Yaku promotes reforestation, watershed management and community environmental awareness. UNCISA is committed to protecting the environment through environmentally responsible tourism, the prevention of destructive extractive practices and the sustainable use of resources. In the Amazon, Kallari promotes certified organic agriculture, based on traditional practices such as composting and the use of bioles, in balance with nature. These actions contribute not only to environmental conservation, but also to the strengthening of territorial and food sovereignty.

The analysis of the drivers of well-being in Imbabura and the Amazon shows a broad organizational capacity and a diversity of strategies adapted to local contexts. These community-based initiatives articulate traditional knowledge and contemporary tools to strengthen economic, social, cultural, and environmental sustainability. In both territories, well-being is built from a logic of autonomy, identity and respect for nature, which reaffirms the need for public policies that recognize, strengthen and accompany these ways of life and organization from a territorial, intercultural and participatory approach.

5.3. Key Understandings for Comprehending Sustainable Wellbeing in Indigenous Communities

According to the information collected in the cases of Imbabura and its organizations (UNORCAC, UNCISA, Symak Yaku) as well as in the case of the Amazon (Kallari), this systematization is presented on the frameworks of understanding on three key concepts

within sustainable well-being (well-being, technology and sustainability), the perception of each organization will be evidenced and also a comparative analysis between the cases of Imbabura and the Amazon.

5.3.1. Understanding of Wellbeing

The notion of Buen Vivir in Ecuador's indigenous communities represents a holistic and deeply interconnected vision of well-being, which goes beyond traditional economic growth. This concept, integrating multiple knowledge and practices, advocates harmonious coexistence with nature, social equity and environmental sustainability. Through the pillars of Sumak Kawsay (wisdom of the man of the forest, village life, and land without evil), these communities promote a lifestyle that seeks to balance the cultural, social, and environmental dimensions. Chassagne (2019), He stresses that the speech highlights the possibility of a necessary change away from the current situation, by promoting, for example, reciprocity and community well-being over individual well-being and human needs achieved through economic growth. Good Living brings together the set of knowledge and practices that imagine and pursue ways of life different from Western modernity, the capitalist system and the discourse of development (Cuestas-Caza et al., 2020).

Table 6. Comparative analysis of wellbeing understanding between Imbabura and Amazonia cases

	Imbabura			Amazon
	UNORCAC	Sumak Yaku	UNCISA	Kallari
Understanding Wellbeing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on Sumak Kawsay, social, economic and environmental balance. • Living in harmony with the environment and with intergenerational responsibility. • Self-sufficiency and social cohesion as the key to prosperity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-being as an integral state, linked to water and nature. • Not only economic improvement but also access to resources without affecting Pachamama. • Water is key to their identity and way of life. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associated with self-management and the improvement of living conditions. • State of economic and social stability that maintains the local culture. • It promotes tourism and respect for culture and the environment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linked to territorial roots and the self-sufficiency of the "chakra". (traditional cultivation plot). • Option to live in harmony without relying on external industries • Happiness and peace come from living in their territory with food self-sufficiency.

<p>Mechanisms to achieve well-being</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on self-management, micro-enterprises and agricultural training. • Infrastructure projects such as community savings banks and bio-businesses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minga and reforestation with native species. • Water conservation and moorlands with infrastructure for constant access. • Environmental education and sustainable agriculture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of basic infrastructure and services such as drinking water and ecotourism. • Self-management through assemblies and mingas strengthens well-being without depending on external institutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The "chakra" is the pillar to achieve well-being. • Food self-sufficiency and connection to the land avoid dependence on the external market. • They reject harmful industries such as mining.
<p>Importance of well-being</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Priority in sustainability for future generations. • It maintains social cohesion and cultural autonomy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsibility towards nature and future generations. • Maintain harmony with the environment and ensure access to essential resources, such as water. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key to preserving cultural identity and economic development. • Ensuring well-being means reducing external dependence and strengthening self-sufficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It ensures that families live off their resources without migration or dependence on external industries. • Well-being is preserving the culture and family roots.

Own Elaboration

Understanding Wellness

In both Imbabura and the Amazon, well-being is conceived as a state that transcends the material and is deeply linked to harmony with nature, cultural identity, and community life. However, each territory brings particular emphasis to this common vision.

- In Imbabura, well-being in UNORCAC and UNCISA is closely related to self-reliance, social cohesion and the balance between economic development, infrastructure and cultural preservation. Sumak Yaku introduces a more marked ecological perspective, where well-being is understood as an integral state, dependent on access to water and respect for nature (Pachamama).
- In the Amazon, particularly in the communities linked to Kallari, well-being is deeply rooted in territorial and food self-sufficiency, sustained by the traditional chakra cultivation system. Here, well-being is associated with the possibility of living in harmony with the environment without depending on external industries. Tranquility, roots in the territory and respect for biodiversity are valued, all embodied in the worldview of Sumak Kawsay.

Mechanisms to Achieve Well-Being

In both contexts, the mechanisms for achieving well-being are based on community self-management practices, the strengthening of local capacities and the sustainable use of natural resources.

1. In Imbabura, UNORCAC and UNCISA promote mechanisms such as the development of basic infrastructure, technical training and the promotion of community enterprises. UNCISA adds tourism and access to basic services as key tools. Sumak Yaku focuses its actions on the conservation of water and high Andean ecosystems through mingas, reforestation and environmental education.
2. In the Amazon, the *chakra* emerges as the fundamental axis of well-being, allowing not only the production of food, but also the transmission of ancestral knowledge. In addition, the Kallari association acts as a platform for technical and commercial support that promotes sustainable production and improves the income of families, reinforcing their independence from the external market.

Importance of Wellbeing

Well-being, in both cases, is understood as a vital principle to ensure cultural continuity, dignity of life and intergenerational sustainability.

1. In Imbabura, well-being is key to preserving cultural identity, strengthening community cohesion and fostering autonomous economic development. The organizations agree that sustainability must benefit both present and future generations, without sacrificing the natural environment or the self-determination of communities.
2. In the Amazon, well-being is inseparable from the protection of the territory, understood not only as a physical space, but as a cultural and spiritual heritage. Ensuring well-being means ensuring that families can sustain themselves with their own resources, without relying on extractive industries. In addition, it is conceived as an act of social and environmental justice, where community and nature coexist reciprocally.

5.2.2. Understanding of Technology

To understand what is the framework of understanding technology from the experience of indigenous communities. Van Kessel & Condori Cruz (1992) proposes an understanding of technology from the indigenous communities from the term Andean technology. Andean technology is not only based on the restoration of a past prestigious for its productive achievements, but it is the starting point for a new development that is inspired by the values and native cultural tradition. This technology is appropriate and adapted from a social,

cultural, ecological, and to some extent, economic perspective. It is questionable whether modern and foreign technology could reach a similar level of adaptation in the Andean region. In addition, Andean technology is its own knowledge, developed over two thousand years through observation and experimentation, allowing the Andean man to handle it independently, without depending on external sources. This makes it the basis for emancipatory development. More than a simple set of techniques, Andean technology is a coherent system, deeply rooted in the Andean worldview, where it is not separated from family and community life, but is integrated into a hierarchy of economic, social, cultural, religious, ethical and affective values that the Andean man respects.

Table 7. Comparative analysis of technology understanding between Imbabura and Amazonia cases

Technology	Imbabura			Amazon
	UNORCAC	Sumak Yaku	UNCISA	Kallari
Perception of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful tool if it respects cultural values. Complement of ancestral practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ally in water management and self-sufficiency. Optimizes without affecting connection with nature. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for economic and community development. Fundamentals in communication and tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical use, but with caution. Distrust of technologies that affect autonomy and culture.
Valued Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agricultural and resource management technologies. Technical training as "soft technology". Economic self-management tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation systems and water automation. Optimization to reduce physical effort. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social networks as a visibility tool. Improvements in basic infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient agricultural tools. Irrigation systems that maximize production. They avoid technologies that affect their autonomy.
Impact of technology on everyday life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved agricultural production and economic management. Strengthens self-sufficiency and fair trade. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It facilitates water management. Reduces workload. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote tourism. Improves community infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase productivity and access to markets. Limited use to preserve autonomy.

Own Elaboration

The use and appreciation of technology in rural and indigenous contexts is profoundly conditioned by cultural relationships with the environment, organizational history, and community development goals. In the case studies of Imbabura and the Amazon, a variety of approaches are observed, ranging from strategic appropriation to critical caution. Three key dimensions are then analyzed: perception, valued technologies, and impacts on everyday life.

Perception of technology

In general terms, community organizations in Imbabura and Amazonia do not reject technology, but evaluate its relevance based on cultural, ecological and autonomy criteria.

1. In Imbabura, UNORCAC recognizes technology as a useful tool as long as it respects cultural values and complements ancestral practices. This vision aligns with an "appropriate technology" approach, where technical knowledge is adapted to the local context. Sumak Yaku, for his part, considers technology as an ally in water management and self-sufficiency, as long as it does not interrupt the harmonious relationship with nature. UNCISA emphasizes the functional value of technology, seeing it as an essential component for economic and community development, particularly in the areas of communication and tourism.
2. In the Amazon, Kallari takes a more critical stance. Although the practical value of certain technologies is recognized, an attitude of caution and distrust prevails towards those that may affect organizational autonomy or erode local culture. This position reflects an active defense of territory and ancestral knowledge against external forms of technological imposition.

Valued technologies

The technologies assessed reflect the strategic priorities of each organisation and its commitment to sustainability and resilience.

1. At UNORCAC, technologies oriented to agricultural production and natural resource management are valued, with an emphasis on technical training understood as soft technology, and on economic management tools that strengthen self-sufficiency. Sumak Yaku emphasizes irrigation systems and water automation, as these technologies allow processes to be optimized without increasing the physical burden of work.
2. UNCISA prioritizes the use of communication technologies, such as social networks for visibility, as well as improvements in basic infrastructure, in line with its orientation towards community-based tourism. In contrast, Kallari values efficient agricultural technologies and irrigation systems geared towards maximizing production without

compromising autonomy. In this sense, the use of technologies that may depend on external agents or substantially modify the way of community life is deliberately avoided.

Impact of technology on everyday life

The impact of technology is reflected in multiple dimensions of community work: production, time management, autonomy, and sustainability.

1. In Imbabura, the technologies promoted by UNORCAC have contributed to improving agricultural production, strengthening the local economy and promoting fair trade. In the case of Sumak Yaku, the use of water technologies has significantly reduced the workload, especially in activities traditionally undertaken by women, and has facilitated the management of resources. UNCISA recognizes in technology the potential to promote tourism and improve communal infrastructure, generating indirect economic benefits.
2. In the Amazon, Kallari sees a positive impact in terms of productivity and market access, albeit with limited technological adoption, mainly aimed at preserving autonomy and local knowledge. This strategic approach allows the organization to adopt what is useful without compromising the cultural and environmental integrity of the communities.

Conclusion

Comparative analysis allows us to show that the understanding of technology in the cases studied is not determined by a merely technical criterion, but deeply contextualized in the cultural, political and ecological relations of each territory. While the organizations of Imbabura tend towards a more pragmatic and functional appropriation of technology, those of the Amazon adopt a stance of selective use, prioritizing the defense of autonomy and ancestral knowledge. This diversity of approaches highlights the need to promote technologies that are culturally appropriate, socially useful and ecologically sustainable, integrating technology as part of the fabric of community life, and not as an external imposition.

5.2.3. Understanding of Sustainability

When seeking to understand sustainability from the perspective of indigenous communities, it is necessary to understand that it is based on harmony with man and his environment. According to Viteri Gualinga (2002) everything starts from Alli Kawsay's understanding within the indigenous communities of the Ecuadorian Amazon. The strength of the Alli Kawsay is based on knowledge, which is fundamental to managing the local ecological and spiritual

bases that sustain and autonomously solve needs. This implies the development of production systems that adapt coherently to the conditions of the environment.

Table 8. Comparative analysis of sustainability understanding between Imbabura and Amazonia cases

Sustainability	Imbabura			Amazon
	UNORCAC	Sumak Yaku	UNCISA	Kallari
Understanding Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on the "Sumak Kawsay", balance between economic well-being and the environment. It includes preservation of resources, social justice and transmission of values. It is an intergenerational obligation to ensure a healthy environment and a sound economy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It focuses on water conservation and its link to life and culture. Sustainability is a responsibility towards Yakumama (Mother Water) and Pachamama (Mother Earth). They promote reforestation and protection of water as the basis of their life. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focused on self-sufficiency and sustainable resource management. It seeks autonomy in the management of water and other essential resources. It promotes sustainable economic development and biodiversity conservation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on food self-sufficiency through the "chakra". They prevent extractive activities that damage the ecosystem. The relationship with the land is a commitment to intergenerational protection.
Practices and Mechanisms for Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of bio-businesses with local products (cocoa, guayusa). Creation of community savings banks. Promotion of organic agricultural practices and biodiversity conservation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reforestation with native species. Use of technology for sustainable water management. The minga as a tool for conservation and environmental education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-management through infrastructure for drinking water and waste treatment. Ecotourism as a source of sustainable income. Mingas and collective work strengthen community sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of the "chakra" for biodiversity and self-sufficiency. Traditional agricultural methods that respect natural cycles. They avoid intensive exploitation and seek to strengthen their connection to the land.
Importance of Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is key to social cohesion and future quality of life. It defends cultural identity and strengthens the local economy. Pillar for the conservation of lands and culture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spiritual and cultural significance in Sumak Yaku. Ensuring access to water and biodiversity is a duty. It is not only a practical necessity, but a sacred responsibility to Pachamama. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Essential for economic independence and cultural preservation. It guarantees economic security and community cohesion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key to a dignified life without depending on extractive industries. Preserving the earth ensures balance for future generations.

Own Elaboration

Sustainability in rural and indigenous contexts is not reduced to a technical or environmental issue, but constitutes a dimension deeply intertwined with culture, territory, local economy and intergenerational relations. In the cases analyzed, a broad and contextualized vision of sustainability is evident, with approaches that articulate respect for nature, community autonomy and social justice. Next, three fundamental axes are analyzed: understanding sustainability, mechanisms and practices to achieve it, and importance attributed to sustainability.

Understanding sustainability

In all cases, sustainability is conceived as an integral principle that articulates community life with the preservation of the environment and cultural transmission.

1. In Imbabura, UNORCAC frames its vision in the concept of *Sumak Kawsay*, understanding sustainability as the balance between economic well-being, social justice and environmental conservation. The need to preserve natural resources is highlighted as an intergenerational duty that guarantees a healthy environment and a solid economy. Sumak Yaku adds spiritual emphasis by relating sustainability to the care of water (*Yaku Mama*) and the land (*Pachamama*), based on reforestation practices and protection of water sources. UNCISA, for its part, focuses on sustainability from self-sufficiency and autonomous management of essential resources, particularly water, promoting a community-centered model of sustainable development.
2. In the Amazon, Kallari expresses a deep territorial and ecological vision, in which sustainability is based on food self-sufficiency guaranteed by the chakra farming system. This organization rejects extractive activities that damage the ecosystem and promote a harmonious relationship with the land, understood as an ethical commitment to future generations.

Practices and mechanisms for sustainability

Sustainable practices in both territories are aimed at guaranteeing productive autonomy, conservation of ecosystems and strengthening community organization.

1. In Imbabura, UNORCAC implements bio-enterprises based on local products (such as cocoa or guayusa), promotes community savings banks and encourages agroecological practices to conserve biodiversity. Sumak Yaku emphasizes reforestation with native species, the use of technologies for water management, and environmental education. The mingas are also highlighted as key tools to strengthen the community fabric. UNCISA applies a strategy focused on the autonomous management of infrastructure (drinking water, waste treatment), ecotourism as a source of sustainable income, and collective work to strengthen sustainability from the local level.

2. In the Amazon, Kallari places the *chakra* system at the center of his proposal. This traditional agroforestry practice not only ensures food self-sufficiency, but also promotes biodiversity and soil regeneration. In addition, they reject extractive and intensive practices, prioritizing agricultural methods that respect natural cycles and reinforce the spiritual and material connection with the land.

Importance of sustainability

In all four cases, sustainability is not conceived only as a pragmatic necessity, but as an essential ethical and cultural principle to guarantee a dignified life and a cohesive community. At UNORCAC, it is valued as a pillar of social cohesion and cultural identity, linked to the defense of the territory and the quality of life of future generations. For Sumak Yaku, sustainability has spiritual and cultural significance, especially in relation to water and biodiversity, and is assumed as a sacred responsibility towards Pachamama. In UNCISA, it is recognized as a necessary condition for economic independence and cultural preservation, also understood as a guarantee of well-being and equity. Finally, in the Amazon, Kallari sees sustainability as the key to maintaining a dignified life without relying on external industries, and as the means to preserve the environment for the benefit of future generations.

Conclusion

The understanding of sustainability in the cases of Imbabura and Amazonia transcends the technical or environmental notion, integrating itself as a structuring principle of collective well-being. The organizations analyzed develop mechanisms and practices that combine ancestral knowledge with contemporary strategies, defending their territorial and cultural autonomy. These visions reaffirm that sustainability, in indigenous and rural contexts, is inseparable from social justice, cultural identity, and reciprocity with nature. Therefore, any development policy that seeks to be effective in these contexts must start from the recognition of these multiple dimensions of sustainability.

6. Reciprocity in Qualitative Research

Reciprocity in qualitative research implies a fundamental shift towards an ethical and responsible approach, especially when working with historically silenced populations. Unlike traditional research methods, in which researchers trained in Western academies tend to privilege academic protocols without paying attention to the practices, culture and values of the participants. Qualitative research with a deep ethical sense requires a posture of respect and reciprocity. Reciprocity recognizes the knowledge shared by the participants as a "gift" that must be valued and reciprocated, not only as a source of data, but as a sign of respect for their knowledge (Lavalleé, 2009). It is critical that qualitative researchers, especially those working with populations of colonial legacies, critically examine and apply decolonizing

methodological practices in their research (Thambinathan & Kinsella, 2021), as this ensures a commitment to give back to communities and to recognize their knowledge and makes it a pillar for ethical and responsible qualitative research.

From this logic, the experiences of the WP3 team of ToBe Ecuador and the joint work that has been carried out with the organizations of indigenous communities of the province of Imbabura to carry out this reciprocity according to their needs are presented.

6.1. UNORCAC

After holding the first workshop with UNORCAC leaders, where drivers and barriers of the communities were validated, the idea of training on the formulation of community development projects was consolidated, since it was a need exposed by the directive. They needed to have people dedicated to being designers, who lead the formulation of the projects and seek competitive funds for improvements within their communities, either to improve current initiatives or to generate new projects that improve the quality of life of the members of each community.

The training was supported by an expert in projects and economic empowerment with extensive experience working with organizations of rural indigenous communities and calls of this nature. Through several meetings between the team and the trainer, the specific needs and requirements of UNORCAC were focused, obtaining the planning and design of the training; Meanwhile, the organization's board was in charge of the call in each community and the management of registrations.

In the first instance, through the application of a survey aimed at the group of young people registered in the call, and a participatory diagnosis, it was identified that:

- Most of the young people were between 23 and 29 years old and almost 90% were university students.
- 60% of young people have not had previous training in project formulation, 34% have a foundation and the remaining 6% do not know about project management.
- 86.7% of the young women expect to have operational training and project start-up to have future financing opportunities.
- 93% wanted to have hands-on training on how to formulate and design a project.
- The young participants consider that project management is a way that will allow them to achieve goals or objectives to improve the well-being of their communities and families.

In relation to these findings, the design of the training plan was carried out under the construction of community actions and common projects proposed by Bansart (1993), whose principles and approach guide the practice of project construction from the community framework, so that:

- The community group analyzes itself to guide its future; In this sense, it is important to know their history and identity in such a way that the processes of autonomy and reflection are framed in deep narratives of the Being.
- The community group is responsible for generating synergies for self-management in favor of collective and relational changes.
- It is necessary to articulate theory and practice in order to reach conceptions that are valid for the entire social context.
- The role of the trainer is to guide the processes in such a way that it is from the community group that the questions, assumptions and strategies of action arise.

In this sense, the work proposal is based on the project management manual defined by Avella (2016) and adapted to the context of the communities belonging to UNORCAC. The training was carried out in 7 face-to-face workshops and 6 virtual sessions, giving a total of 40 hours in which the topics shown in Table 1 were implemented.

Table 9. Training Plan for Community Project Formulation at UNORCAC

Workshop	Topics	Hours	Modality
1	Presentation, identification and definition of key concepts for the development of a project	4	In-person
2	Brainstorming and participatory diagnosis	2	Online
3	Problem Tree, Prioritization, and Solutions	4	In-person
4	Review of problems and prioritization of alternatives	2	Online
5	Feasibility analysis, goal tree	4	In-person
6	Actor Mapping	2	Online
7	Logical framework development and concept note development	4	In-person
8	Concept Note Review	2	Online
9	Financial Planning	2	Online
10	Action Plan and Gantt Matrix	2	Online
11	Timeline, logical framework and first activities	4	In-person
12	Launch of the first activities	4	In-person

Own elaboration

The face-to-face sessions were held at the "Jambi Mascari" communal house, Cotacachi parish. In constant communication with the participants, the work agenda was established, the face-to-face activities were carried out on Saturdays in July and August from 9:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. (with a break at 11:00 a.m.); Likewise, the online sessions were developed in the months of July and August on Wednesdays of each week, considering the Internet connection and the availability of the participants.

For the inauguration, an ancestral ceremony was held, represented by the symbols of the Kichwa community, then, the president of the organization intervened who highlighted the importance of this training of designers to seek new initiatives in the communities.

The necessary supplies for the training were organized by the Ecuador team together with those assigned to the UNORCAC board; flip charts, markers, blackboard, some laptops were used and refreshments were coordinated for breaks in face-to-face sessions. Likewise, an attendance list was kept where the participants in each session signed.

Although the workshops were able to carry out all the planned activities, the punctuality of the participants and the availability of spaces presented challenges; however, the ability to comply with the phases of the workshop in relation to the definition of the problems, objectives, activities and planning of actions, were reflected in three proposals for group projects proposed in relation to three fundamental axes identified by the participants where problems in most of the communities were focused, These axes are: social, environmental and economic. In addition, the formal presentation of a community project with funding to the Secretariat for the Development of Indigenous, Afro-Ecuadorian and Montubia Peoples and Nationalities was prepared, under a format established by the same organization.

Figure 12. Image set: Workshop development

To close the last face-to-face session, a ceremony of the Kichwa culture was held to thank for this experience; in addition, certificates were given for 40 hours to the participants. Finally, a *pambamesa* (communal food table) was shared to close this experience that enriched the members of UNORCAC and the ToBe Ecuador team.

The training workshops in project design and formulation allowed young people to:

- Clearly define the objectives of the project, delimit its scope, stipulate actions and their way of measuring and establish schedules of activities and responsibilities.
- Break down the project into phases, tasks, and activities, creating a logical and organized structure.

- Ability to identify and analyze project needs, as well as available resources (financial, human, technical).
- Ability to identify key stakeholders, understand their needs and interests, and develop strategies to engage them effectively.

The training managed to contribute to the knowledge of design and formulation of projects under practical tools applied in the field of community development. This experience also motivated the confidence and empowerment of young people to apply for real financing opportunities. The acquisition of knowledge and skills to identify, plan and execute initiatives allows them to respond in an organized way to their specific needs; thus improving their ability to manage resources and make autonomous decisions.

It is for this reason that the group of young people, together with the UNORCAC board, decided to design a joint project and apply for a call for financing of productive development projects offered by the Secretariat of Management and Development of Peoples and Nationalities for approximately USD 400,000. The team of young people designed a project to increase the productive capacity of the Sumak Mikuy company (owned by UNORCAC) to strengthen the productive and agro-industrial community development of the peasant communities of the province of Imbabura.

This is how our participation in the design and execution of this training workshop in the design and formulation of community projects has materialized with this group of young people who decided to move from theory to action and generate proposals to improve their communities and thus achieve an adequate quality of life. Under this experience of living a process of reciprocal and responsible research, it allows researchers to have an ethical awareness of how to generate knowledge, giving a contribution to society from other means other than economic retribution.

6.2. UNCISA

In the case of the Union of Indigenous Communities of San Rafael, it collaborated with one of its objectives at the time, the maintenance and improvement of the community cemetery. For this, in conversation with the leaders, the acquisition of pine trees was coordinated, which were planted in the cemetery by means of a minga, representing reciprocity and attending to their need.

In line with the sense of reciprocity mentioned above, in May 2024, the ToBe Ecuador team delivered a set of pine trees to the community to contribute to the development of their cemetery, according to their needs. These pine trees will help transform the space into a more comfortable and attractive place for visitors, becoming a tourist place that respects and

enhances the cultural value of the community. This action responds to the commitment to collaborate in significant projects for the community, thus reinforcing the bonds of respect and mutual support established since the beginning of our relationship with UNCISA.

Figure 13. Image set: ToBe Ecuador team delivering pine trees to UNCISA

6.3. Sumak Yaku

The first approach in Sumak Yaku was carried out in December 2023, where there was a visit and observation of the place, observation of the processes of water storage and distribution, conversation with operators, interviews with members of the board and observation of a community assembly.

In constant communication with the water board board, two primary needs were presented: to collect geographic information from users and to obtain a website to help them with management activities. For this, we had the support of a specialist in georeferencing, and after two months a geographic information system was developed and a web page supported by a geoportal that integrates the collected data was designed and implemented. A control panel was developed that allows the visualization and analysis of information, improving decision-making. The integration of the database with the user registry has made it possible to visualize the geographical distribution and efficiently manage resources.

The process for Sumak Yaku's deliverables was divided into two key phases, each with specific activities that integrated georeferencing tools, database design, web application

development, and data visualization into a geoportal. These phases are detailed below, incorporating references to the figures that illustrate each step.

Phase 1: Systematization of Data for the Update of the User Cadastre

This phase consisted of the collection and organization of geospatial and alphanumeric data using a Geographic Information System (GIS) and mobile tools for field capture. The following activities were carried out:

1. **Questionnaire Review:** A thorough review of the questionnaire was conducted for data collection, making improvements to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the information captured.
2. **Implementation of Forms in QGIS:** Using QGIS, custom forms were structured that facilitated the capture of georeferenced and alphanumeric data. During this phase, QGIS was synchronized with the QField and Mergin Maps mobile applications, conducting pilot tests to ensure the effectiveness of the form in the field.
3. **Socialization with the Sumak Yaku Team:** Coordinated with the Sumak Yaku team of enumerators in Otavalo, delimiting specific sectors in each community to organize data capture.
4. **Mergin Maps Training:** Training sessions were given for operators in the use of Mergin Maps, with the aim of enabling them to record geospatial data efficiently in the field.
5. **Field Data Capture:** Operators traveled predefined routes to record user and household information, including geolocation and water and sanitation data. Eight specific users received permissions in Mergin Maps for efficient distribution of responsibilities.
6. **Data Synchronization:** On a daily basis, the captured data was synchronized between Mergin Maps and QGIS, allowing for a smooth transfer of information.

Figure 14. Image set: implementation of Phase 1

Phase 2: Design and Implementation of a Website for the Sumak Yaku Drinking Water Board with Geoportal Support

In this phase, a web platform was developed that allows the storage, visualization and analysis of the collected data. This platform integrates an interactive geoportal that facilitates decision-making and resource management.

1. **Database Configuration:** The database was designed in MySQL, creating a secure structure to store user information and water board records.
2. **Frontend and Backend Development:** An intuitive frontend was created using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, and a robust backend in PHP to handle authentication and connection to the database.
3. **Control Panel Design:** The platform's control panel allows administrators to view and manage detailed information about each community. This dashboard includes a table with records for 4051 users.
4. **Integration of Users and Surveys in the Database:** The integration of user data and surveys allows you to count the number of users in each community, displaying a summary in the dashboard.
5. **Implementing the Geoportal with Leaflet.js:** The geoportal, developed with Leaflet.js, allows an interactive visualization of the distribution of users on a map. It offers specific tools, such as search by ID number (CI) and pop-ups that show user details when they click on the map.

6. **Preliminary Data Visualizer:** As an additional product, a preliminary data visualizer was created, available online, which allows a review of the data collected prior to full implementation. This visualizer is shown in Figure 30.
7. **Products Reached and Geospatial Visualization:** In addition to the revised questionnaire, customized form in QGIS, and a GeoPackage (GPKG) file with the data collected, the project includes thematic maps that represent the geographic distribution of users

Figure 15. Image set: Implementation of Phase2

Data management and control has been strengthened thanks to the acquisition of a hosting service, which allows the Sumak Yaku board to store and manage its information efficiently. This hosting offers total control over the data, facilitating accessibility and guaranteeing the security of the information managed by the organization.

The incorporation of geospatial technology has been key in this project. The implementation of tools such as the Geographic Information System (GIS) has allowed an accurate representation of users and their locations, optimizing the management of geographic data and improving the ability to visualize the distribution of water users.

This project marks the beginning of a significant advance in water management. The foundations laid will allow the Sumak Yaku Drinking Water Board to integrate even more advanced systems in the future, which will expand the capacities for monitoring and controlling water resources. In addition, the integration of these technologies promotes greater community participation. The ease of capturing and visualizing data not only optimizes processes, but also ensures more transparent management, fostering community trust and collaboration in decision-making.

The delivery of the two products for the drinking water board of Sumak Yaku took place on September 12, 2024, in which a letter of commitment was signed with the organization's board of directors, to collaborate in future research, thus strengthening the commitment to carry out joint projects.

Figure 16. Image set: ToBe Ecuador team formally delivering developed products to Sumak Yaku

Through these actions, we aimed to contribute to improving the management of organizations representing community members while also supporting the strengthening of their processes

of autonomy and decolonial praxis as a foundation for the reorientation of community life and resistance against the asymmetries of the capitalist system (Garcia-Arias & Cuestas-Caza, 2024). In conclusion, the activities carried out with the Indigenous organizations in Imbabura that collaborated in collecting qualitative data for WP3-ToBe reflect an ethical commitment to research grounded in principles of respect, responsibility, and reciprocity, seeking to transcend traditional academic protocols.

7. Conclusions

The work carried out by the ToBe Ecuador team in 2024 has significantly contributed to a situated understanding of sustainable wellbeing in Indigenous contexts in the country. Through the analysis of four community-based experiences in the provinces of Imbabura and Napo, this report captures plural visions of wellbeing, sustainability, and technology, as well as the tensions between those visions and existing legal and policy frameworks.

Among the main findings, shared structural barriers include institutional fragmentation, weak policy implementation, limited infrastructure and financing, and the persistence of extractivist models that affect local territories. However, enabling factors also emerged, such as ancestral knowledge, community-based organizational structures, solidarity economies, and a strong spiritual and practical connection to nature—elements that are essential for the development of transformative indicators.

The conceptions of wellbeing expressed by participating communities differ markedly from Western growth-centered paradigms, pointing instead to relational, ethical, and place-based forms of living. These insights offer critical inputs for rethinking ToBe's conceptual frameworks and for informing public policy approaches that value epistemic plurality and diverse ways of life.

The report also underscores the importance of reciprocity in qualitative research—not only as an ethical principle, but also as a methodological practice that fosters horizontal relationships, strengthens community ownership of research findings, and ensures the social relevance of knowledge production. The feedback activities conducted in the field helped validate and co-construct the findings, reinforcing the project's commitment to participatory and context-sensitive methodologies.

In sum, the Ecuadorian case provides valuable empirical evidence for the overarching objectives of the ToBe project, particularly in advancing the development of indicators that reflect territorial dynamics, community values, and collective aspirations for wellbeing. It also invites continued dialogue among communities, researchers, and institutions to co-create transition pathways toward more sustainable, just, and resilient societies.

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